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ABSTRACT

We study sparse recovery in an ultra-coherent dictionary formed by one algebraic singular atom and an orthonormal polynomial block. The key geometric quantity is a separation margin $\kappa(\alpha, K)$, defined as the $L^2(\mu)$ distance between the normalized singular atom and the polynomial subspace, together with its uniform version κ_{pop} . We show that the population support-block minimum eigenvalue is lower bounded at the κ_{pop}^2 scale through the Friedrichs-angle geometry. For finite samples, entry-wise concentration gives a sufficient sample size with quadratic dependence on sparsity s , logarithmic dependence on dictionary size D , and inverse quartic dependence on κ_{pop} . Under a support-block small-ball condition with constants (p_0, u_0) , the dependence on s improves to linear up to logarithmic factors. This improvement is conditional, and uniform analytic lower bounds for Jacobi ensembles with $K \sim s$ are currently unavailable. Numerical diagnostics report $p_0 \approx 0.781$ at $u_0 = 0.1$ for $s = 20$, and fourth-moment growth $\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}} \sim s^{1.809}$, which supports anti-concentration as the relevant mechanism in this regime.

1. Introduction

1.1. Dictionary Geometry and the Friedrichs Angle

This paper studies a foundational computational problem in singular approximation. When a singular atom and a polynomial subspace are nearly collinear, the statistical complexity of sparse recovery is controlled by geometric separation. We measure this separation by the distance from x^α to P_K , or equivalently by the Friedrichs angle.

Algebraic singularities of the form x^α , $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, appear in many model problems:

- **Elliptic PDEs with corners:** Solutions to the Laplace or Poisson equation on polygonal domains exhibit corner singularities $u(r, \theta) \sim r^\alpha \psi(\theta)$ where $\alpha = \pi/\theta_0$ depends on the corner angle θ_0 [19].
- **Fracture mechanics:** Crack-tip stress fields behave as $\sigma \sim r^{-1/2}$ (i.e., $\alpha = 1/2$), fundamental to computing stress intensity factors.
- **Boundary layers:** Singular perturbation problems generate boundary layers with algebraic structure near domain boundaries.

In each case, polynomial approximation near the endpoint $x = 0$ controls numerical difficulty. This is a classical source of instability in spectral methods and polynomial expansions.

From 1D radial to multi-dimensional geometry. We focus on the radial model x^α in one dimension. This is the core component in corner singularities $u(r, \theta) \sim r^\alpha \psi(\theta)$ after separation of variables. The same approximation barrier appears in higher dimensions through the radial part. Section 3 reports a 2D corner benchmark that is consistent with this reduction.

We use a dictionary $\mathcal{D} = \{\psi_\alpha : \alpha \in \mathcal{A}_{\text{grid}}\} \cup \{\phi_j\}_{j=1}^K$ with singular atoms and polynomial atoms. The geometric quantity that controls the analysis is the Friedrichs angle between x^α and P_K :

$$\cos \theta_F = \sup_{p \in P_K} \frac{|\langle x^\alpha, p \rangle|}{\|x^\alpha\| \|p\|}. \quad (1)$$

When $\theta_F \rightarrow 0$, global coherence criteria lose predictive value.

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1.2. The Müntz–Szász Rate as Geometric Control

The classical Müntz–Szász theorem [5] gives density/completeness criteria for power systems. In the weighted $L^2(\mu)$ setting, we use the quantitative separation rate (proved in Appendix A.1):

$$\kappa(\alpha, K) := \inf_{p \in P_K} \left\| \frac{x^\alpha}{\|x^\alpha\|_{L^2(\mu)}} - p \right\|_{L^2(\mu)} \asymp K^{-(\alpha+\beta/2+1/2)}. \quad (2)$$

For a candidate set $\mathcal{A} \subset (0, 1)$, we define the uniform margin

$$\kappa_{\text{pop}} := \inf_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \kappa(\alpha, K).$$

This rate is the central geometric control in the paper. Even when global mutual coherence satisfies $\mu(D) \rightarrow 1$, the pointwise separation satisfies $\sin \theta_F \sim \kappa(\alpha, K)$, and the worst-case analysis is controlled by κ_{pop} . Therefore the problem remains analyzable through a quantitative approximation parameter.

1.3. From Geometric Separation to Sparse Recovery

We study the sparse regression model

$$y_i = u(x_i) + \varepsilon_i, \quad u(x) = c_1^* x^{\alpha^*} + \sum_{j=2}^s c_j^* \phi_j(x), \quad i = 1, \dots, N. \quad (3)$$

The question is how N scales with the geometry of the dictionary.

Standard mutual incoherence conditions fail in this regime since $\mu(D)$ is close to one. Our framework replaces global coherence by local geometric separation. We prove that the support-block restricted eigenvalue satisfies

$$\lambda_{\min}(\Sigma_{S^*}) \gtrsim \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2,$$

and this yields finite sample bounds with dominant dependence κ_{pop}^{-4} .

1.4. Contributions

The paper provides the following contributions:

1. **Geometric parameterization of ultra-coherent recovery.** We identify κ_{pop} as the effective local margin and derive its weighted Müntz–Szász scaling, $\kappa_{\text{pop}} \asymp K^{-(\alpha+\beta/2+1/2)}$, in the Jacobi type setting.
2. **Population support-block curvature from Friedrichs geometry.** We prove an explicit support-block eigenvalue formula and lower bound: $\lambda_{\min}(\Sigma_{S^*}) = 1 - \|\rho\|_2 \geq \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/2$.
3. **Finite sample guarantees and lower bound comparison.** We obtain $N \gtrsim s^2 \kappa_{\text{pop}}^{-4} \log D$ via entry-wise concentration and compare this with detection lower bounds in Appendix A.7.
4. **Conditional anti-concentration route.** Under support-block small-ball constants (p_0, u_0) , Corollary 19 gives $N \gtrsim s \log(s/\delta)/(p_0 u_0^2 \kappa_{\text{pop}}^4)$. We state this result explicitly as conditional and provide numerical evidence for (p_0, u_0) in Section 3.
5. **Fourth-moment and small-ball diagnostics.** In the normalized Jacobi regime $K = s$, we report $\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}} \sim s^{1.809}$ together with support-block small-ball estimates. These diagnostics explain why fourth-moment closure is conservative here.
6. **Reproducible empirical study of the theory-practice gap.** We quantify the gap between worst case sufficient bounds and observed phase thresholds, separating geometric effects (κ_{pop} versus $\kappa(\alpha^*)$) from concentration conservatism.

Connection to open problems in symbolic regression. In a companion note [15], Open Problem 1 asks when symbolic methods can recover the singular exponent in polynomial time. The present paper isolates one rigorous component of that question. We characterize the information requirement for sparse selection in a fixed candidate grid and show how this requirement is controlled by κ_{pop} .

Regime of validity. The upper bounds are sufficient conditions with explicit constants. They are conservative in difficult regimes with $\mu \approx 0.997$. The experiments show much smaller practical sample sizes. Remark 28 decomposes this gap and shows that the stable part of the theory is the scaling law $N \sim \kappa_{\text{pop}}^{-4}$.

1.5. Related Work

Classical approximation theory and Müntz–Szász. The Müntz–Szász theorem characterizes approximation by powers. We use its quantitative weighted L^2 form through Borwein and Erdélyi [5]. The endpoint behavior of orthogonal polynomial systems under Jacobi type weights is classical in the sense of Szegő and Nevai [26, 24]. Our setting uses this endpoint structure at $x = 0$ as the source of near collinearity.

Compressed sensing in infinite-dimensional and structured settings. Adcock, Hansen, Poon, and collaborators [1, 2] have developed a comprehensive framework for compressive sensing in infinite-dimensional function spaces, including structured sparsity models, asymptotic incoherence, and multi-level sampling strategies. Their work demonstrates that coherence can be managed through structured subsampling. Our setting differs fundamentally: the coherence is *intrinsic* to the dictionary geometry (algebraic singularities approaching polynomials) rather than arising from discretization. We exploit the *quantitative rate* of this coherence decay via Müntz–Szász theory rather than asymptotic incoherence.

Geometry beyond incoherence. Standard coherence conditions [12, 29] are not informative when $\mu \rightarrow 1$. Our argument is closer to geometric restricted eigenvalue analysis [4] with a problem specific separation parameter. This perspective treats sparse recovery as a geometric conditioning problem rather than a global coherence problem.

Minimum-separation viewpoints in related inverse problems. Super-resolution and line spectral estimation also replace global incoherence by local geometric separation conditions. Representative examples include minimum-separation analysis for spikes and spectral lines [7, 9, 10]. Our setting is different in model class and observation operator, but the structural role is analogous: a geometric margin controls stable discrimination when atoms are strongly correlated. This comparison helps explain why κ_{pop} is the correct local complexity parameter in the present dictionary.

Information based complexity viewpoint. Our minimax statements follow the logic of information based complexity: identify the information radius before discussing a specific optimizer. This viewpoint is standard in computational complexity for continuous problems [28] and matches the role of κ_{pop} in this paper.

Coherent dictionaries and alternative recovery conditions. Elad and Bruckstein [14], Gribonval and Nielsen [18], and Tropp and Gilbert [30] gave recovery guarantees under refined coherence conditions. Our result is complementary. It is driven by the approximation rate of singular atoms toward polynomial spaces, not by coherence magnitude itself.

Analysis sparsity and D-RIP frameworks. The analysis sparsity line based on D-RIP is central for coherent dictionaries because it targets stable signal recovery even when synthesis coefficients are not identifiable. In our setting the sampling operator is induced by random design points under μ , and the main objective is singular atom identification in a synthesis model with an explicitly constructed polynomial block. For this reason D-RIP is not the main lens here. The role played by D-RIP constants in analysis models is replaced by the local geometric margin κ_{pop} in our support-block restricted eigenvalue argument.

Matrix concentration and small-ball methods. Matrix Bernstein inequalities [31] and effective rank concentration [21] motivate improvements over the entry-wise s^2 factor. Small-ball methods [23, 22] provide an alternative route under weaker moment assumptions. We give a conditional support-block small-ball theorem and numerical validation in the Jacobi ensemble; proving a uniform analytic lower bound for p_0 as $K \rightarrow \infty$ remains open.

1.6. Organization

Section 2 presents the main theoretical results. Section 3 provides numerical experiments validating the theory. Appendices A–F contain complete proofs. A notation summary follows in Table 1.

1.7. Modeling Assumption: Dictionary Construction

We assume the dictionary $D = \{\psi_k\}_{k=1}^D$ is constructed as follows:

- **Singular atoms:** A finite grid $\{\alpha_m\}_{m=1}^M \subset (0, 1)$ with spacing $\Delta_\alpha > 0$, where one grid point $\alpha_{m_0} = \alpha^*$ matches the true exponent. Dictionary includes $\psi_m(x) = x^{\alpha_m}$ (normalized in $L^2(\mu)$).
- **Smooth atoms:** An *orthonormal* polynomial basis for $P_K = \text{span}\{x^k : 0 \leq k \leq K\}$, constructed via Jacobi polynomials $P_k^{(\beta,b)}$ or QR factorization of the monomial basis (see Assumption 2 and Remark 6). We emphasize

Table 1
Notation summary

Symbol	Meaning
α	Singular exponent, $\alpha \in (0, 1)$
β	Weight exponent in $w(x) \geq c_0 x^\beta$
K	Polynomial degree
s	Sparsity level
D	Dictionary size
N	Sample size
$\mu(\mathcal{D})$	Mutual coherence $\max_{j \neq k} \langle \psi_j, \psi_k \rangle $
$\kappa(\alpha)$	Pointwise separation $\inf_{p \in P_K} \ \psi_\alpha - p\ _{L^2(\mu)}$ at exponent α
κ_{pop}	Uniform separation $\inf_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \kappa(\alpha)$
Δ	SSC gap (Singular Separation Condition)
Σ_{S^*}	Gram submatrix restricted to support S^*
γ	Restricted eigenvalue constant
L	Atom boundedness constant $\sup_x \psi_k(x) $

that the raw monomial basis $\{x^k\}$ is **not** used directly, as its Gram matrix is an exponentially ill-conditioned Hilbert-type matrix (Appendix A.7); the orthonormalization step is essential for all theoretical guarantees.

Remark 1 (Grid spacing and mutual coherence). *The spacing Δ_α controls mutual coherence between neighboring power-law atoms. We require Δ_α chosen appropriately so that:*

1. *The Müntz–Szász separation $\kappa(\alpha_m)$ is bounded away from zero uniformly for $m \in \{1, \dots, M\}$;*
2. *For $m \neq m_0$, the correlation $|\langle x^{\alpha_m}, u \rangle_\mu|$ is strictly smaller than $|\langle x^{\alpha^*}, u \rangle_\mu|$ by a gap $\Delta > 0$ (Singular Separation Condition).*

Formal analysis of the grid spacing and its effect on κ_{pop} and Δ appears in Appendix A.5.

2. Main Results

2.1. Algebraic Separation (Müntz–Szász)

Assumption 1 (Weighted measure). μ is a probability measure on $[0, 1]$ with density $w(x) = \frac{d\mu}{dx}$ satisfying:

- (i) **Near-origin lower bound:** $w(x) \geq c_0 x^\beta$ for all $x \in (0, \delta]$, for constants $c_0 > 0$, $\delta \in (0, 1)$, and $\beta \geq 0$.
- (ii) **Global upper bound:** $w \in L^\infty([0, 1])$, i.e. $\|w\|_{L^\infty} < \infty$.

Remark 2 (Role of each bound and admissible weights). *Condition (i) ensures that μ charges the origin heavily enough for the Müntz–Szász separation (Lemma 4): x^α concentrates near $x = 0$, and the weight must be present there. Condition (ii) provides the normalization upper bound $\|x^\alpha\|_{L^2(\mu)}^2 \leq \|w\|_{L^\infty} / (2\alpha + 1)$ (Lemma 36).*

Admissible weight examples: *The restriction $\beta \geq 0$ ensures compatibility between the lower bound $w(x) \geq c_0 x^\beta$ and the global boundedness condition. Examples include:*

- **Jacobi-type weights:** $w(x) = c x^\beta (1-x)^b$ with $\beta, b \geq 0$, c chosen for normalization. For $\beta = 0.55, b = 0$, we have $\|w\|_{L^\infty} = c < \infty$.
- **Truncated power laws:** $w(x) \propto \min(x^\beta, M)$ with $\beta \geq 0$ and truncation $M < \infty$ near $x = 1$ (ensuring integrability).

Note that the lower bound $w(x) \geq c_0 x^\beta$ does not require w to behave like x^β globally; it only controls the weight near the origin. The theory accommodates any bounded modification away from $x = 0$.

Compatibility with cited approximation results. *The quoted Borwein–Erdélyi theorem (Theorem 34 in Appendix A.1) requires $\beta > -1$. Our working regime $\beta \geq 0$ is a strict subset of that range, so the approximation theorem applies directly. The boundedness requirement $\|w\|_{L^\infty} < \infty$ is imposed independently by Assumption 1(ii), and is*

used only in the normalization bound of Lemma 36. The separation rate statement itself follows from the weighted approximation theorem plus the near-origin lower bound in Assumption 1(i). Extending to $\beta \in (-1, 0)$ is possible if one replaces the global L^∞ normalization step by a weighted normalization argument.

Remark 3 (Robustness to weight misspecification). *In practice, the sampling weight μ may not be known exactly. Suppose the orthogonal polynomial basis $\{\phi_j\}$ is constructed with respect to a reference weight μ_0 (e.g. Jacobi with parameter β_0), but the actual data are drawn from μ with $\mu \neq \mu_0$. The resulting Gram matrix Σ_{smooth} deviates from the identity: $\|\Sigma_{\text{smooth}} - I_K\|_{\text{op}} \leq \|d\mu/d\mu_0 - 1\|_{L^\infty}$. Provided $\|d\mu/d\mu_0 - 1\|_{L^\infty} < \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/(4s)$, the RE condition is maintained with a degraded constant $\gamma' = \gamma - s\|\Sigma_{\text{smooth}} - I_K\|_{\text{op}} > 0$. Thus the framework is robust to small perturbations in μ (including uncertainty in β); the critical quantity is the local power-law exponent β near $x = 0$ that controls the Müntz–Szász separation, not the global shape of w . Sensitivity experiments (Section 3) confirm that moderate perturbations of β around its nominal value produce graceful degradation in detection accuracy.*

Relaxation via small-ball methods. The stringent tolerance $\|d\mu/d\mu_0 - 1\|_{L^\infty} < \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/(4s)$ comes from the entry-wise perturbation route. Corollary 19 gives a conditional support-block alternative: under

$$\inf_{\|v\|_2=1} \mathbb{P}(|\langle v, \psi_{S^*}(x) \rangle| \geq u_0) \geq p_0,$$

it suffices that

$$N \gtrsim \frac{s \log(2s/\delta)}{p_0 u_0^2 \kappa_{\text{pop}}^4}.$$

This route bypasses exact empirical orthonormality and replaces the strong L^∞ mismatch requirement by anti-concentration constants (u_0, p_0) that can be estimated from pilot samples. The remaining open step is a uniform analytic lower bound for p_0 in the Jacobi regime $K \sim s$.

Lemma 4 (Weighted Müntz–Szász separation). *Fix $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and let μ satisfy Assumption 1. Define*

$$P_K := \text{span}\{x^k : 0 \leq k \leq K\}, \quad \psi_1(x) := \frac{x^\alpha}{\|x^\alpha\|_{L^2(\mu)}}.$$

Then there exists a constant

$$C_{\text{sep}} = C_{\text{sep}}(\alpha, \beta, c_0, \delta, \|w\|_{L^\infty}) > 0$$

such that

$$\kappa(\alpha) := \inf_{p \in P_K} \|\psi_1 - p\|_{L^2(\mu)} \geq C_{\text{sep}} K^{-\nu}, \quad \nu := \alpha + \frac{\beta}{2} + \frac{1}{2}. \quad (4)$$

Proof. Appendix A.1 gives the full derivation. The proof combines:

1. a weighted approximation lower bound for x^α in $L^2([0, 1], x^\beta dx)$ from Borwein–Erdélyi,
2. transfer from $x^\beta dx$ to $d\mu = w(x) dx$ using $w(x) \geq c_0 x^\beta$ on $(0, \delta]$,
3. normalization of x^α in $L^2(\mu)$ using $\|w\|_{L^\infty}$.

This yields the stated exponent $\nu = \alpha + \beta/2 + 1/2$ and constant C_{sep} . □

Remark 5 (Self-contained definition of $\kappa(\alpha)$ and κ_{pop}). *The separation parameters are central to all results. We collect their characterizations:*

- **Pointwise distance:** $\kappa(\alpha) := \inf_{p \in P_K} \|\psi_\alpha - p\|_{L^2(\mu)}$, i.e., the $L^2(\mu)$ -distance from the normalized singular atom $\psi_\alpha = x^\alpha / \|x^\alpha\|_{L^2(\mu)}$ to the polynomial subspace P_K .
- **Friedrichs angle:** $\kappa(\alpha) = \sin \theta_{\alpha, K}$, where $\theta_{\alpha, K}$ is the angle between ψ_α and P_K . This is the sine of the Friedrichs angle between $\text{span}\{\psi_\alpha\}$ and P_K .
- **Uniform margin:** $\kappa_{\text{pop}} := \inf_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \kappa(\alpha)$ enters the worst-case theory; the pointwise value $\kappa(\alpha^*)$ governs instance-specific performance (typically $\kappa(\alpha^*) \gg \kappa_{\text{pop}}$; see Section 3).
- **Rate:** By Lemma 4, $\kappa(\alpha) \geq C_{\text{sep}} K^{-(\alpha+\beta/2+1/2)}$. Under uniform constants over $\alpha \in \mathcal{A}$, this yields a corresponding lower bound for κ_{pop} . The exponent is negative, so the separation decreases as K grows.

2.2. Restricted Eigenvalue via Geometric Separation

Assumption 2 (Orthonormal smooth atoms). *The smooth dictionary atoms $\{\psi_k\}_{k=2}^{D_{\text{smooth}}+1} \subset P_K$ are orthonormal in $L^2(\mu)$:*

$$\langle \psi_j, \psi_k \rangle_{L^2(\mu)} = \delta_{jk} \quad \text{for all } j, k \in \{2, \dots, D_{\text{smooth}} + 1\}. \quad (5)$$

Consequently, for any subset $S_{\text{smooth}} \subset \{2, \dots, D\}$ of smooth atoms, the Gram submatrix satisfies $\Sigma_{S_{\text{smooth}}, S_{\text{smooth}}} = I_{|S_{\text{smooth}}|}$, and in particular $\lambda_{\min}^{\text{smooth}} = 1$.

Assumption 3 (Sparsity-degree compatibility and atom boundedness). *We assume:*

- (i) **Smooth support contained in polynomials:** $S_{\text{smooth}} \subset \{0, 1, \dots, K\}$, so the smooth part of the support uses at most $s - 1 \leq K + 1$ orthonormal polynomial atoms.
- (ii) **Bounded dictionary atoms:** There exists $L = L(K, \alpha_{\min}, \alpha_{\max}, \beta, b, c_0, \delta, \|w\|_{L^\infty}) > 0$ such that $|\psi_k(x)| \leq L$ for all $x \in [0, 1]$ and all atoms $k \in \{1, \dots, D\}$. For singular atoms $\psi_\alpha(x) = x^\alpha / \|x^\alpha\|_{L^2(\mu)}$, we use

$$\|\psi_\alpha\|_{L^\infty} = \frac{1}{\|x^\alpha\|_{L^2(\mu)}} \leq \left(\frac{2\alpha + \beta + 1}{c_0 \delta^{2\alpha + \beta + 1}} \right)^{1/2},$$

hence

$$L_{\text{sing}} := \sup_{\alpha \in [\alpha_{\min}, \alpha_{\max}]} \left(\frac{2\alpha + \beta + 1}{c_0 \delta^{2\alpha + \beta + 1}} \right)^{1/2} < \infty.$$

For $L^2(\mu)$ -orthonormal Jacobi atoms ϕ_k , we use the standard endpoint growth envelope

$$\|\phi_k\|_{L^\infty([0,1])} \leq C_{\beta,b} k^\tau, \quad \tau := \max\{\beta, b\} + \frac{1}{2},$$

see classical Jacobi polynomial asymptotics [26]. Hence $L_{\text{poly}} = O(K^\tau)$ and $L = \max\{L_{\text{sing}}, C_{\beta,b} K^\tau\}$.

K-dependence of L: The concentration term in Lemma 9 scales as $L^2 s^2 / \kappa_{\text{pop}}^4$, so the polynomial envelope contributes a factor $K^{2\tau}$. In the experimentally relevant regime ($\beta = 0.55$, $b = 0$), $\tau \approx 1.05$ gives moderate finite-K inflation (for $K = 8$, this remains a constant-level penalty). This explicit K-dependence is part of the theory-practice gap discussed in Remark 28.

Under (i), Lemma 4 applies with $K \geq s - 1$, giving $\kappa_{\text{pop}} \geq C \cdot s^{-(\alpha + \beta/2 + 1/2)}$ when $K \sim s$.

Impact of K-dependent L: Since the sufficient sample complexity scales as $L^2 s^2 / \kappa_{\text{pop}}^4$, the envelope contributes $K^{2\tau}$. Under the common coupling $K \sim s$, this becomes an additional $s^{2\tau}$ multiplicative factor in front of κ_{pop}^{-4} . For fixed K , L is constant and the stated s^2 dependence is unchanged.

Remark 6 (Realizing orthonormality: known vs. estimated weights). *Assumption 2 is not satisfied by the monomial basis $\{x^k\}_{k=0}^K$, whose Gram matrix (a generalized Hilbert matrix) has $\lambda_{\min} \sim e^{-cK}$ (Appendix A.7, Proposition therein). It is satisfied by the shifted Jacobi polynomial basis $\phi_k(x) = P_k^{(\beta,b)}(2x - 1) / \|P_k^{(\beta,b)}\|_{L^2(\mu)}$, which is orthonormal in $L^2(\mu)$ by construction (Appendix A.7, A.7.2). All theoretical results below assume this orthonormal choice. In numerics, orthogonality is enforced via `scipy.special.eval_jacobi` or QR factorization.*

Data-driven construction when μ is unknown. When the sampling weight μ is unknown, we construct an approximately orthonormal smooth basis from pilot samples:

1. Collect N_{pilot} samples $\{x_i\}_{i=1}^{N_{\text{pilot}}}$ from the (unknown) sampling distribution.
2. Form the empirical Gram matrix of the monomial basis: $\hat{G}_{jk} = \frac{1}{N_{\text{pilot}}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{pilot}}} x_i^{j+k}$.
3. Compute the eigendecomposition $\hat{G} = U D U^\top$ and define $\phi_k(x) = \sum_{j=0}^K U_{jk} x^j / \sqrt{D_{kk}}$.

Finite-sample bound and error propagation. Let $Z_i = m(x_i)m(x_i)^\top$ where $m(x) = (1, x, \dots, x^K)^\top$. By covariance-operator concentration with intrinsic dimension (effective rank) [21], $\|\hat{G} - G\|_{\text{op}} \leq \epsilon$ with probability $1 - \delta$ when

$$N_{\text{pilot}} \gtrsim \frac{\|G\|_{\text{op}}^2}{\epsilon^2} \left(r_{\text{eff}}(G) + \log(1/\delta) \right), \quad r_{\text{eff}}(G) = \frac{\text{tr}(G)}{\|G\|_{\text{op}}}.$$

This replaces the crude K^2 scaling by an intrinsic-dimension term and is typically much smaller in practice.

Let $\gamma = \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/2$ be the population support-block RE constant from Theorem 8. If orthogonalization error is $\epsilon = \|\hat{\Sigma}_{\text{smooth}} - I\|_{\text{op}}$, then the effective support-block curvature satisfies

$$\gamma_{\text{eff}} = \gamma - s\epsilon - O(\sqrt{s\epsilon}),$$

where the $O(\sqrt{s\epsilon})$ term comes from perturbed singular–smooth cross terms. To keep $\gamma_{\text{eff}} \geq \gamma/2$, it is sufficient to enforce $\epsilon \lesssim \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/(8s)$.

Practical regime used in our experiments: we do not estimate a full unknown density; we sample from a known parametric family and use the corresponding shifted Jacobi basis directly. In this regime, pilot estimation is only used as a diagnostic and the observed orthogonality defect is small.

Remark 7 (Population-to-empirical orthogonality gap). Assumption 2 requires population-level orthonormality: $\langle \psi_j, \psi_k \rangle_{L^2(\mu)} = \delta_{jk}$. In practice, we observe the empirical Gram matrix $\hat{\Sigma}_{jk} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \psi_j(x_i)\psi_k(x_i)$, which is random and only approximately orthonormal. The transfer from population to empirical RE is handled by Lemma 9: for the smooth block, $\|\hat{\Sigma}_{\text{smooth}} - I\|_{\text{op}} \leq s \cdot \|\hat{\Sigma}_{\text{smooth}} - I\|_{\text{max}}$, and by the Bernstein bound with $N \gtrsim L^2 s^2 \log(s/\delta)/\epsilon^2$, the empirical smooth block satisfies $\hat{\Sigma}_{\text{smooth}} \geq (1 - \epsilon)I$ with high probability. This is a standard perturbation argument; we do not assume empirical exact orthonormality.

Theorem 8 (Restricted eigenvalue of support-block). Under Assumptions 1 and 2, let $S^* = \{1\} \cup S_{\text{smooth}}$ with $|S^*| = s$. Define $\Sigma_{S^*} \in \mathbb{R}^{s \times s}$ as the population Gram submatrix restricted to S^* . Write

$$\Sigma_{S^*} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \rho^\top \\ \rho & I_{s-1} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \rho := \Sigma_{S_{\text{smooth}}, 1}.$$

Then

$$\lambda_{\min}(\Sigma_{S^*}) = 1 - \|\rho\|_2 \geq 1 - \sqrt{1 - \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2} \geq \frac{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2}{2}, \quad (6)$$

where $\kappa_{\text{pop}} := \inf_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \kappa(\alpha)$ (Remark 5).

Consequently, for $v \in C(S^*, 3) := \{v : \|v_{(S^*)^c}\|_1 \leq 3\|v_{S^*}\|_1\}$ and $\Sigma = \mathbb{E}_{x \sim \mu}[\psi(x)\psi(x)^\top]$,

$$v^\top \Sigma v \geq \frac{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2}{2} \|v_{S^*}\|_2^2. \quad (7)$$

Proof. Full proof in Appendix A.2.

Step 1 (exact spectrum of the support-block). By Assumption 2, the smooth block is identity. Decompose $\mathbb{R}^{s-1} = \text{span}\{\rho\} \oplus \ker(\rho^\top)$. On $\ker(\rho^\top)$, the eigenvalue is 1 (multiplicity $s - 2$). On $\text{span}\{e_1, \rho\}$, the two eigenvalues are $1 \pm \|\rho\|_2$. Hence

$$\lambda_{\min}(\Sigma_{S^*}) = 1 - \|\rho\|_2.$$

By Lemma 39 (Bessel's inequality),

$$\|\rho\|_2^2 \leq \|\text{proj}_{P_K} \psi_1\|^2 = 1 - \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2,$$

so $\|\rho\|_2 \leq \sqrt{1 - \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2}$, and therefore

$$\lambda_{\min}(\Sigma_{S^*}) \geq 1 - \sqrt{1 - \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2} \geq \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/2.$$

Step 2 (Cone lower bound via Pythagorean decomposition). For $v \in C(S^*, 3)$, write $f_v = \sum_k v_k \psi_k$ and decompose $\psi_1 = \psi_1^\perp + p^*$ with $\psi_1^\perp \perp P_K$ and $\|\psi_1^\perp\| = \kappa_{\text{pop}}$. Since all other atoms lie in P_K (smooth atoms by construction; off-support singular atoms are handled via their P_K -projections),

$$v^\top \Sigma v = \|f_v\|_{L^2(\mu)}^2 \geq v_1^2 \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2 + \|v_1 p^* + \sum_{j \neq 1} v_j \psi_j\|^2 \geq v_{S^*}^\top \Sigma_{S^*} v_{S^*} \geq \frac{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2}{2} \|v_{S^*}\|_2^2.$$

The second inequality follows because the P_K -component $g = v_1 p^* + \sum_{j \neq 1} v_j \psi_j$ is orthogonal to ψ_1^\perp , so the norms add by Pythagoras, and dropping the off-support atoms from g only reduces the norm of the P_K projection (details in Appendix A.2). \square

2.3. Empirical RE via Concentration

Lemma 9 (Sample complexity for empirical RE (entry-wise Bernstein)). *Suppose each atom satisfies $|\psi_k(x)| \leq L$ for all $x \in [0, 1]$. Let $\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*} = \frac{1}{N} \Phi_{S^*}^\top \Phi_{S^*}$ be the empirical Gram submatrix on the support S^* .*

If

$$N \geq \frac{64L^2 s^2 \log(2s/\delta)}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4}, \quad (8)$$

then with probability at least $1 - \delta$, $\lambda_{\min}(\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*}) \geq \frac{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2}{4}$.

Proof. See Appendix A.3. The proof applies scalar Bernstein entry-wise to the s^2 entries of $\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*} - \Sigma_{S^*}$, uses $\|\cdot\|_{\text{op}} \leq s \|\cdot\|_{\max}$, and sets $t = \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/(4s)$. \square

Proposition 10 (Rigorous fixed- K matrix Bernstein bound). *Assume, in addition to Assumptions 1, 2, and 3, that for the support-block feature vector $\psi_{S^*}(x) \in \mathbb{R}^s$:*

$$v_{S^*} := \left\| \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\psi_{S^*}(x) \psi_{S^*}(x)^\top - \Sigma_{S^*} \right)^2 \right] \right\|_{\text{op}} \leq C_K s \quad (9)$$

for a constant C_K independent of s, N, D , and

$$\|\psi_{S^*}(x)\|_2^2 \leq sL^2 \quad \text{a.s.} \quad (10)$$

Then there is a universal constant $C > 0$ such that if

$$N \geq C \log \frac{2s}{\delta} \left(\frac{C_K s}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4} + \frac{sL^2}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2} \right), \quad (11)$$

we have

$$\lambda_{\min}(\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*}) \geq \frac{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2}{4} \quad (12)$$

with probability at least $1 - \delta$.

Proof. See Appendix A.3.5. The proof applies Tropp's matrix Bernstein inequality to $X_i = \psi_{S^*}(x_i) \psi_{S^*}(x_i)^\top - \Sigma_{S^*}$ with target tolerance $t = \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/4$, then combines the perturbation bound with Theorem 8. Since $\kappa_{\text{pop}} \leq 1$, this gives the fixed- K scaling order $N \gtrsim s \log(s/\delta) \kappa_{\text{pop}}^{-4}$. \square

Remark 11 (Matrix concentration route for $K \sim s$). *Proposition 10 gives a rigorous improvement route in fixed- K settings. For the practically important coupling $K \sim s$, the main bottleneck is controlling the variance proxy*

$$\left\| \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbb{E} \left[\left(\psi(x_i) \psi(x_i)^\top - \Sigma \right)^2 \right] \right\|_{\text{op}},$$

which reduces to fourth-order moments of polynomial features on S^* . Appendix A.3.5 provides a rigorous coarse $s^{3/2}$ bound and the corresponding sample complexity consequence.

Remark 12 (Fourth moment scaling: partial theory and numerics). *For the natural regime $K \sim s$, the variance proxy depends on $\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}}$ where $\mathbf{B}_{jk} = \mathbb{E}[\psi_j^2 \psi_k^2]$ is the fourth-moment matrix. We have two levels of control:*

- A rigorous coarse bound in Appendix A.3.5, Proposition 45:

$$\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}} \leq C_{\beta,b} s^{3/2}.$$

- Numerical computation for the normalized Jacobi ensemble with $\beta = 0.55$:

$$\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}} \sim s^{1.809}, \quad s \in \{5, 10, 20, 50\}. \quad (13)$$

The rigorous $s^{3/2}$ bound gives

$$N \gtrsim \frac{s^{3/2} \log(s/\delta)}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4}. \quad (14)$$

The empirical exponent gives

$$N \gtrsim \frac{s^{1.809} \text{polylog}(s)}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4}. \quad (15)$$

In this regime, fourth moments do not explain the near-linear empirical phase transitions. This is why we introduce a separate anti-concentration route (Corollary 19).

Remark 13 (Implicit sparsity condition and conservative constants). *The concentration argument requires the perturbation tolerance $t = \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/(4s)$ to satisfy $t \leq 1$ (used in simplifying the Bernstein denominator), equivalently $s \geq \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/4$. For $\kappa_{\text{pop}} = 0.021$, this gives $s \geq 1.1 \times 10^{-4}$, trivially satisfied. However, a more stringent implicit condition arises from requiring the sufficient sample size to be finite: the bound $N \geq 64L^2 s^2 \log(2s^2/\delta)/\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4$ yields $N = O(10^{10})$ for $s = 5$, $\kappa_{\text{pop}} = 0.021$, $L = 1$, $\delta = 0.05$. This is a highly conservative sufficient condition, as it predicts a sample size far exceeding practical experiments. This conservatism is intrinsic to worst-case entry-wise Bernstein bounds in the ultra-coherent regime (see Remark 28 for a quantitative decomposition).*

We emphasize that the bound is mathematically valid: any N exceeding this threshold guarantees recovery with probability $\geq 1 - \delta$, but the constant is not tight. The theory's primary value lies in identifying the correct scaling law $N \sim \kappa_{\text{pop}}^{-4}$; this structural dependence, rather than the absolute constant, captures the fundamental cost of near-collinearity between singular and polynomial atoms.

Remark 14 (Improved scaling via matrix concentration). *By concentrating the $s \times s$ support-block rather than the full $D \times D$ Gram matrix, the sample complexity improves from $O(s^4 \log D/\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4)$ to $O(s^2 \log s/\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4)$. The dominant factor κ_{pop}^{-4} remains; this is an inherent cost of the small Friedrichs angle between singular and polynomial subspaces. For the dual feasibility (off-support atoms), a separate union bound over D atoms introduces $\log D$, appearing only in the SSC term (Theorem 18).*

Potential improvement via matrix Bernstein: Proposition 10 already gives a rigorous fixed- K improvement based on matrix Bernstein. When K scales with s , Appendix A.3.5 provides a rigorous coarse bound $N \gtrsim s^{3/2} \log s/\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4$, while the normalized numerical diagnostic gives exponent 1.809 for $\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}}$. This supports using small-ball anti-concentration rather than fourth moments to reach linear-in- s scaling.

The theoretical bound $N \sim s^2/\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4$ is a sufficient condition; numerical experiments (Section 3) show that far fewer samples suffice in practice, indicating that the Bernstein bound is conservative for the structured distributions arising here.

2.4. Support Recovery via Primal-Dual Witness

Definition 15 (Singular Separation Condition (SSC)). *For a signal $u = \sum_{j \in S^*} c_j^* \psi_j$, the Singular Separation Condition holds with gap $\Delta > 0$ if the correlation of the true singular atom ψ_1 with the signal exceeds that of any confuser atom by at least Δ :*

$$|\langle \psi_1, u \rangle_\mu| \geq \max_{k \notin S^*} |\langle \psi_k, u \rangle_\mu| + \Delta. \quad (16)$$

Theoretical role: The SSC is a **sufficient condition** for dual certificate existence in the primal-dual witness (PDW) construction. It serves as an analytical tool that isolates the geometric property (correlation gap) governing detection success, analogous to how the irrepresentable condition isolates the property governing support recovery in standard LASSO theory. Like the irrepresentable condition, SSC is:

- **Sufficient but not necessary:** LASSO can succeed even when SSC is violated (Section 3 shows 69% success rate when $\Delta_{\text{SSC}} \leq 0$).
- **Signal-dependent:** It depends on the coefficients $\{c_j^*\}$, not just the dictionary geometry.
- **Conservative:** The sufficient condition is very strict ($|c_1^*| > 10^5$) under worst-case bounds, while practice requires $|c_1^*| = O(1)$.

We state theorems conditional on SSC to identify the structural mechanism (correlation gap) enabling detection; this does not claim that SSC must hold for all signals of interest.

Remark 16 (SSC as structured irrepresentability). SSC can be viewed as a population-level irrepresentability condition specialized to the singular-plus-smooth structure. A sufficient condition in terms of model parameters is:

$$|c_1^*| \cdot \kappa_{\text{pop}} - \left\| \Sigma_{(S^*)^c, S^*} \Sigma_{S^*, S^*}^{-1} \text{sign}(c_{S^*}^*) \right\|_{\infty} \geq \Delta. \quad (17)$$

See Appendix A.6 for the derivation.

Remark 17 (SSC: sufficient but not necessary). The SSC gap $\Delta_{\text{SSC}} > 0$ requires a minimum signal strength $|c_1^*| \gtrsim 2.4 \times 10^5$ under worst-case bounds (Proposition 52). **This sufficient condition is highly conservative for typical signals, and it is not necessary for recovery.** Empirically (Section 3), detection succeeds at 69% when $\Delta_{\text{SSC}} \leq 0$, rising to 92% at large N , confirming that the **geometric separation** $\kappa_{\text{pop}} > 0$ (Lemma 4), not the SSC, is the fundamental enabler. The SSC serves as a safety margin for adversarial signal constructions, analogous to the irrepresentable condition in standard LASSO theory [6].

More precisely, by Proposition 52, a sufficient condition for $\Delta_{\text{SSC}} > 0$ is:

$$|c_1^*| > \frac{4 \|c_{\text{smooth}}\|_1 \sqrt{1 - \underline{\kappa}^2}}{c_{\min} (\Delta\alpha)^2}, \quad (18)$$

where c_{\min} is the curvature constant (Remark 51) and $\underline{\kappa}$ is the uniform Müntz–Szász separation. With experimental values ($c_{\min} \approx 0.085$, $\Delta\alpha = 0.02$, $\underline{\kappa} \approx 0.026$, $\|c_{\text{smooth}}\|_1 \approx 2$), this gives $|c_1^*| \gtrsim 2.4 \times 10^5$, which is conservative because $\sqrt{1 - \underline{\kappa}^2} \approx 0.9997$ in this ultra-coherent regime. In practice, $|c_1^*| = 1.4$ suffices because: (i) the pointwise $\kappa(\alpha^*)$ is much larger than $\underline{\kappa}$, and (ii) favorable geometry (smooth components nearly orthogonal to the nearest confuser) reduces the cross-contamination well below the worst-case bound.

Practical verification via pilot samples. In practice, one can estimate Δ_{SSC} from a pilot dataset of size N_{pilot} :

1. **Compute empirical correlations:** For each candidate atom ψ_k , calculate $\hat{\rho}_k = \frac{1}{N_{\text{pilot}}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{pilot}}} \psi_k(x_i) y_i$, where y_i are the noisy observations.
2. **Identify the maximum:** Let $\hat{k} = \arg \max_k |\hat{\rho}_k|$ and $\hat{\rho}_{\max} = |\hat{\rho}_{\hat{k}}|$.
3. **Estimate the gap:** Compute $\hat{\Delta} = \hat{\rho}_{\max} - \max_{k \neq \hat{k}} |\hat{\rho}_k|$.
4. **Reliability check:** If $N_{\text{pilot}} \gtrsim \sigma^2 \log D / \hat{\Delta}^2$, the estimate is reliable; otherwise, use a finer grid or increase pilot samples.

If the true signal strength $|c_1^*|$ is unknown, one can use a lower bound ρ_{\min} based on domain knowledge (e.g., minimum expected singularity amplitude in crack-tip analysis). The procedure defaults to a finer grid when $\hat{\Delta} < \Delta_{\min}$ for a user-specified threshold.

Theorem 18 (Singular atom detection and coefficient estimation). *Under Assumptions 1, 2, 3, and Definition 15, set*

$$\lambda_N = 4\sigma \sqrt{\frac{\log D + \log(1/\delta)}{N}} \quad (19)$$

(the standard LASSO regularisation calibrated to the noise level σ and dictionary size D).

Main result (rigorous but conservative): *Under the current analysis based on entry-wise Bernstein concentration (Lemma 9), if*

$$N \geq C_1 \frac{s^2 \log(s/\delta)}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4} \quad (20)$$

with $C_1 = 64L^2$, then the RE condition holds with $\lambda_{\min}(\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*}) \geq \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/4$.

Improved bounds (theoretical progress and open problems):

- **Fixed K regime:** Proposition 10 gives a rigorous matrix Bernstein bound with sample complexity of order $N \gtrsim s \log(s)/\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4$ under an explicit fourth moment condition. A complete appendix proof is given in Proposition 44, including the variance proxy calculation and the trace based fourth moment control step.
- **$K \sim s$ regime:** Proposition 45 gives the rigorous coarse bound $\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}} \leq Cs^{3/2}$, which yields $N \gtrsim s^{3/2} \log(s)/\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4$. In the normalized $K = s$ ensemble, we observe $\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}} \sim s^{1.809}$ (Section B), which does not improve the fourth-moment route.
- **Small-ball route (conditional):** Corollary 19 gives $N \gtrsim s \log(s/\delta)/(p_0 u_0^2 \kappa_{\text{pop}}^4)$ under a support-block small-ball condition.

For detection guarantees, if the sample size satisfies the entry-wise bound above and additionally

$$N \geq C_2 \frac{\sigma^2 \log D}{\Delta^2}$$

for SSC dual feasibility (with C_2 depending on L), then with probability at least $1 - \delta$, the LASSO estimator \hat{c} satisfies:

1. **Singular atom detection:** $1 \in \text{supp}(\hat{c})$ (singular atom selected with correct sign);
2. **Coefficient estimation:** $\|\hat{c}_{S^*} - c_{S^*}^*\|_2 \leq \frac{8\sigma\sqrt{s}}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2} \sqrt{\frac{\log D + \log(1/\delta)}{N}}$.

Note: This theorem guarantees singular atom detection (item 1), not exact recovery of the full support S^* . The smooth atoms in S^* may not be recovered exactly due to high coherence; see Remark 20 below.

The first sample complexity term controls restricted eigenvalue concentration (Lemma 9); the second controls dual feasibility via SSC (Lemma 47).

Corollary 19 (Conditional support-block small-ball improvement). *Conditional on the support-block small-ball assumption (21), and under Assumptions 1, 2, 3, and Definition 15, let $u = \psi_{S^*}(x) \in \mathbb{R}^s$ be the support-block design vector. Assume there exist constants $u_0 > 0$ and $p_0 \in (0, 1]$ such that*

$$\inf_{\|v\|_2=1} \mathbb{P}(|\langle v, u \rangle| \geq u_0) \geq p_0. \quad (21)$$

Then there is a constant $C_{\text{sb}} > 0$ such that

$$N \geq C_{\text{sb}} \frac{s \log(2s/\delta)}{p_0 u_0^2 \kappa_{\text{pop}}^4} \quad (22)$$

implies $\lambda_{\min}(\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*}) \geq \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/4$ with probability at least $1 - \delta$. Consequently, together with $N \geq C_2 \sigma^2 \log D / \Delta^2$, the singular-detection conclusion of Theorem 18 holds.

In particular, if (p_0, u_0) are bounded away from zero uniformly in s , the concentration term is linear in s up to logarithms.

Proof sketch. Apply Mendelson’s small-ball method on the fixed support class

$$\mathcal{F}_{S^*} := \{x \mapsto \langle v, \psi_{S^*}(x) \rangle : \|v\|_2 = 1\}.$$

For each v , Theorem 8 gives

$$\mathbb{E}\langle v, \psi_{S^*}(x) \rangle^2 = v^\top \Sigma_{S^*} v \geq \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/2.$$

Hence the relevant small-ball level in this class is of order $u_0 \kappa_{\text{pop}}$, and the quadratic lower-tail term is of order $p_0 u_0^2 \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2$. The empirical process fluctuation on an s -dimensional support-block is $O(\sqrt{s/N})$. Requiring this fluctuation to be at most a fixed fraction of κ_{pop}^2 yields

$$N \gtrsim \frac{s \log(2s/\delta)}{p_0 u_0^2 \kappa_{\text{pop}}^4}.$$

This gives $\lambda_{\min}(\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*}) \geq \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/4$, and the PDW dual-feasibility step is identical to Theorem 18. \square

Proof of Theorem 18. See Appendix A.4 for full details. The proof requires only **support-block RE**, not full cone RE: we need $\lambda_{\min}(\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*}) \geq \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/4$ (from Lemma 9), not a bound on $v^\top \hat{\Sigma} v$ over the entire cone $C(S^*, 3)$.

Why support-block RE suffices: Standard LASSO analysis often requires the RE condition on the cone $C(S^*, 3) = \{v : \|v_{(S^*)^c}\|_1 \leq 3\|v_{S^*}\|_1\}$, which introduces an additional s factor because the RE constant degrades as $\gamma \sim \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/s$ for vectors with spread-out support. However, our primal–dual witness construction only needs to control the estimation error on the *fixed* support-block S^* , not over the entire cone. The support-block RE constant $\lambda_{\min}(\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*})$ is independent of s (up to concentration), which is why the sample complexity in (13) contains s^2 rather than s^3 . This decoupling is possible because: (i) the smooth atoms are orthonormal, giving exact control of the smooth-smooth Gram submatrix; (ii) the singular atom’s separation κ_{pop} provides a uniform lower bound on the Schur complement; and (iii) the off-support dual feasibility is handled separately via the SSC, not via cone RE.

The proof constructs a primal-dual certificate (\tilde{c}, \tilde{z}) :

1. Solve the restricted LASSO on S^* to get \tilde{c}_{S^*} ; set $\tilde{c}_{(S^*)^c} = 0$. By support-block RE, $\|\tilde{c} - c^*\|_2 \leq 16\sqrt{s}\lambda_N/\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2$.
2. Define $\tilde{z}_{S^*} = \text{sign}(c_{S^*}^*) + \frac{1}{\lambda_N N} \Phi_{S^*}^\top \xi$ and $\tilde{z}_{(S^*)^c} = \frac{1}{\lambda_N N} \Phi_{(S^*)^c}^\top (y - \Phi_{S^*} \tilde{c}_{S^*})$.
3. For $k = 1$, use SSC plus concentration to show $|\tilde{z}_1| = 1$ with correct sign (Lemma 47).
4. For $k \notin S^*$, bound the cross-correlation using Lemma 48 to show $|\tilde{z}_k| < 1 - \eta$ for $\eta = \Delta/(2\lambda_N)$.
5. Invoke standard PDW theorem to conclude. \square

Remark 20 (Singular detection vs. exact support recovery). *Theorem 18 guarantees singular atom detection (selection of $\psi_1 = x^*$), not exact recovery of the full support S^* . This distinction is essential in the ultra-coherent regime:*

- **Detection** requires only the SSC gap condition ($|c_1^*| \kappa_{\text{pop}} > \Delta$);
- **Full recovery** requires the irrepresentable condition for all smooth atoms, which fails when $\mu(D) \approx 1$.

Table ?? confirms this experimentally: singular detection achieves $\approx 100\%$ while full recovery remains at $\approx 0\%$ for moderate N .

2.5. Phase Transition

Theorem 21 (Phase transition).

There exist constants $C_{\text{high}} > 0$ (depending on L) such that:

- **Success regime (proved):** If $N \geq C_{\text{high}} \cdot \max\left(\frac{s^2 \log s}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4}, \frac{\sigma^2 \log D}{\Delta^2}\right)$, then $\mathbb{P}(\text{supp}(\hat{c}) \ni 1) \geq 1 - D^{-1}$.
- **Necessary condition (information-theoretic):** Any estimator \hat{S} satisfying $\mathbb{P}(1 \in \hat{S}) \geq 1/2$ requires $N \geq c \cdot \frac{\log D}{\Delta^2}$ for a universal constant $c > 0$.

Remark 22 (On the necessary condition). *The necessary condition follows from a standard Fano/Le Cam argument: to distinguish the hypothesis H_0 : “atom 1 is detected” from H_k : “atom k is detected instead,” $k \in (S^*)^c$, requires the empirical correlations to resolve a gap of order Δ . With σ -subgaussian noise and D hypotheses, the testing radius is $\sigma\sqrt{\log D/N}$, yielding $N \gtrsim \sigma^2 \log D/\Delta^2$. A complete proof via Fano’s inequality appears in Appendix A.4 (Proposition therein).*

Note on detection vs. exact support recovery: *The necessary condition is for singular atom detection (testing whether index 1 is active), not for exact support recovery (identifying all s active atoms). Exact recovery would require resolving $\binom{D}{s}$ hypotheses, leading to $N \gtrsim \sigma^2 s \log(D/s)/\Delta^2$. We state the simpler detection bound since singular atom identification is our primary goal.*

Remark 23 (Consistency of the κ_{pop}^{-4} scaling across statements). *Since $\kappa_{\text{pop}} \sim s^{-(\alpha+\beta/2+1/2)}$ when $K \sim s$ (Assumption 3(i)), the sample complexity bounds translate to:*

- **Entry-wise bound:** $N \gtrsim s^2 \kappa_{\text{pop}}^{-4} = s^{4\nu+2}$ where $\nu = \alpha + \beta/2 + 1/2$.
- **Matrix bound (fixed K):** $N \gtrsim s \kappa_{\text{pop}}^{-4} = s^{4\nu+1}$.
- **Matrix bound (rigorous, $K \sim s$):** $N \gtrsim s^{1.5} \kappa_{\text{pop}}^{-4} = s^{4\nu+1.5}$.
- **Matrix bound (empirical, normalized $K \sim s$):** $N \gtrsim s^{1.809} \kappa_{\text{pop}}^{-4} = s^{4\nu+1.809}$.
- **Small-ball bound (conditional):** $N \gtrsim \frac{s \log(s/\delta)}{p_0 u_0^2} \kappa_{\text{pop}}^{-4} = \frac{s^{4\nu+1} \log(s/\delta)}{p_0 u_0^2}$.
- **Lower bound:** $N \gtrsim \kappa_{\text{pop}}^{-4} = s^{4\nu}$.

The gap between upper and lower bounds depends on the concentration tool:

- **Entry-wise:** gap of s^2 .
- **Matrix (fixed K):** gap of s .
- **Matrix (rigorous, $K \sim s$):** gap of $s^{1.5}$.
- **Matrix (empirical, normalized $K \sim s$):** gap of $s^{1.809}$.
- **Small-ball (conditional):** gap of $s/(p_0 u_0^2)$, i.e. linear in s when p_0, u_0 are constants.

The dominant scaling $s^{4\nu}$ is common to all, confirming that the geometric cost of ultra-coherent recovery is captured by κ_{pop}^{-4} . The small-ball route gives the sharpest available upper scaling in s for this regime; proving the small-ball constant analytically remains open.

Remark 24 (Gap between sufficient and lower bounds). *The sufficient condition (Theorem 18) requires $N \gtrsim s^2/\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4$, while the information-theoretic lower bound (Theorem 63) requires only $N \gtrsim 1/\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4$. **This gap highlights room for sharper concentration arguments:** narrowing it requires sharper bounds on the fourth-moment structure of Jacobi polynomials (Remark 12), which relates to classical questions on Christoffel function asymptotics and Clebsch–Gordan coefficients for orthogonal polynomial ensembles.*

Sources of the gap. *The s^2 factor arises from:*

1. **Entry-wise concentration:** *Our proof uses scalar Bernstein on s^2 matrix entries, then bounds $\|\cdot\|_{\text{op}} \leq s \|\cdot\|_{\text{max}}$.*
2. **Fourth-moment structure:** *Matrix Bernstein would replace s^2 with $s \log s$ if we could bound $\|\mathbb{E}[(\psi\psi^\top - \Sigma)^2]\|_{\text{op}}$. This requires controlling fourth moments $\mathbb{E}[\psi_j \psi_k \psi_l \psi_m]$ for Jacobi polynomials.*

Path forward: anti-concentration instead of fourth moments. *Proposition 45 gives the rigorous bound $\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}} \leq C s^{1.5}$. In our normalized $K = s$ diagnostic, we observe $\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}} \sim s^{1.809}$ on $s \in \{5, 10, 20, 50\}$, indicating that fourth-moment control is not the mechanism yielding linear-in- s behavior in this ensemble. This motivates the small-ball route of Corollary 19, which replaces fourth-moment variance control by anti-concentration constants (u_0, p_0) .*

What remains open:

- **Analytic small-ball constants:** Prove a uniform lower bound $p_0 > 0$ for (21) in the Jacobi $K \sim s$ regime.
- **Fourth-moment structure:** Characterize when $\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}}$ can be sub- $s^{1.5}$, and whether the observed 1.809 exponent is asymptotic or finite-size.
- **Instance-adaptive bounds:** Replace uniform κ_{pop} by pointwise $\kappa(\alpha^*)$ in non-asymptotic guarantees.

We conjecture that the practical support-block concentration rate is governed by anti-concentration (small-ball) rather than by global fourth moments.

Remark 25 (Decoupling of mechanisms). *The result reveals that:*

1. **Geometry** (κ_{pop}): Controls support-block curvature $\gamma_{\text{sb}} \sim \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2$ and thus on-support estimation error.
2. **Statistics** (Δ): Controls sample complexity for support recovery via correlation gap.

Even as $D \rightarrow \infty$ (global coherence $\mu(D) \rightarrow 1$), recovery remains possible because κ_{pop} and Δ depend on population geometry, not dictionary size.

Remark 26 (Explicit Δ - κ_{pop} - $\Delta\alpha$ Relationship). *Proposition 52 (Appendix A.7) shows that the SSC gap satisfies $\Delta_{\text{SSC}} \geq |c_1^*| \epsilon_{\min} (\Delta\alpha)^2 / 2 - 2\|c_{\text{smooth}}\|_1 \sqrt{1 - \underline{\kappa}^2} - C_3 |c_1^*| |\Delta\alpha|^3$, where ϵ_{\min} is the curvature constant and $\underline{\kappa} = \inf_{\alpha} \kappa(\alpha)$. In the regime where the singular component dominates the smooth contamination (Eq. (78)), we have $\Delta_{\text{SSC}} \asymp |c_1^*| \epsilon_{\min} (\Delta\alpha)^2$. Substituting into Theorem 18 yields the combined sample complexity (Appendix A.7, Corollary therein):*

$$N \gtrsim \max \left\{ \underbrace{\frac{s^2 L^2}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4}}_{\text{concentration}}, \underbrace{\frac{\sigma^2 \log D}{|c_1^*|^2 \epsilon_{\min}^2 (\Delta\alpha)^4}}_{\text{dual feasibility}} \right\}. \quad (23)$$

Curvature constant ϵ_{\min} . The constant $\epsilon_{\min} = \frac{1}{2} \inf_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \mathcal{I}(\alpha)$ derives from the Fisher information metric of the parametric family $\{\psi_{\alpha}\}$. Specifically, for the Jacobi-type weight $w(x) = x^{\beta}(1-x)^b$ on $[0, 1]$:

$$\mathcal{I}(\alpha) = \psi^{(1)}(2\alpha + 1) - \psi^{(1)}(2\alpha + \beta + b + 2),$$

where $\psi^{(1)}$ is the trigamma function (the second derivative of $\log \Gamma$). This follows from differentiating the log-correlation $\ln \langle \psi_{\alpha}, \psi_{\alpha+\delta} \rangle_w$ twice at $\delta = 0$ and using the integral representation of the digamma function. For our experimental parameters ($\beta = 0.55$, $b = 0$, $\mathcal{A} = [0.1, 0.9]$):

$$\epsilon_{\min} = \frac{1}{2} [\psi^{(1)}(2 \cdot 0.9 + 1) - \psi^{(1)}(2 \cdot 0.9 + 2.55)] = \frac{1}{2} [\psi^{(1)}(2.8) - \psi^{(1)}(4.35)] \approx \frac{1}{2} (0.43 - 0.26) = 0.085.$$

Quadratic approximation validity. The approximation $\Delta \propto (\Delta\alpha)^2$ holds when the grid spacing satisfies $|\Delta\alpha| < \epsilon_{\min} / (2C_3) \approx 0.1$, where C_3 bounds the third derivative of the log-correlation (via the tetragamma function). For our fine grid with $\Delta\alpha = 0.02$, the cubic remainder is negligible ($< 2\%$ of the quadratic term).

The first term in (23) encodes the geometric cost of the coherent dictionary (via κ_{pop}), while the second term encodes the statistical cost of resolving the singular atom above noise (via the SSC gap). Both terms share the $(\Delta\alpha)^{-4}$ scaling through the identity $\kappa_{\text{pop}} \asymp K^{-(\alpha+\beta/2+1/2)}$ and the phase-transition condition $\Delta \propto (\Delta\alpha)^2$.

Remark 27 (Off-grid robustness). *When the true exponent α^* does not lie exactly on the grid \mathcal{A} , the LASSO selects the nearest grid point α_{m_0} . Proposition 53 (Appendix A.7) bounds the resulting estimation bias: $\|\text{Bias}\|_2 \leq 2|c_1^*| L_{\max} \epsilon / \gamma$, where $\epsilon = \min_m |\alpha^* - \alpha_m|$ and $L_{\max} = \sup_{\alpha} \sqrt{\mathcal{I}(\alpha)}$ is the Fisher information envelope. Experiments confirm graceful degradation: with $\alpha^* = 0.37$ on a grid of spacing $\Delta\alpha = 0.05$, the RMSE increases by only 3% relative to the on-grid case (Section 3).*

Remark 28 (The κ_{pop}^{-4} Scaling Law: Theory as Explainer, Not Predictor). *The theoretical sample complexity $N_{\text{suff}} = 64L^2s^2 \log(2s^2/\delta)/\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4 = O(10^{10})$ (with $s = 5$, $\kappa_{\text{pop}} \approx 0.021$ in the small-ball calibration protocol, $L \approx 1$ using normalized units, $\delta = 0.05$) exceeds the empirical success threshold $N_{\text{emp}} \leq 420$ by a large factor. The main role of the theory is therefore to identify the **scaling law** $N \sim \kappa_{\text{pop}}^{-4}$, rather than to predict absolute sample sizes. The gap can be quantitatively decomposed into two sources:*

(i) **Pointwise vs. uniform κ (factor $\sim 2.2 \times 10^5$ in N):** *The theorem uses the uniform separation $\kappa_{\text{pop}} = \inf_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \kappa(\alpha) \approx 0.021$, representing the worst-case separation over all grid points. The experiments operate at $\alpha^* = 0.35$ where the pointwise separation $\kappa_{\text{point}}(\alpha^*) := \inf_{p \in P_K} \|\psi_{\alpha^*} - p\|_{L^2(\mu)}$ gives $\kappa_{\text{point}}(0.35) \approx 0.459$. The ratio*

$$r := \frac{\kappa_{\text{point}}(0.35)}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}} \approx \frac{0.459}{0.021} \approx 21.76, \quad r^4 \approx 2.2 \times 10^5.$$

Since $N \sim \kappa^{-4}$, using $\kappa_{\text{point}}(0.35)$ instead of κ_{pop} reduces the sample complexity by $r^4 \approx 2.2 \times 10^5$. This alone moves the prediction from $O(10^{10})$ to about $O(10^5)$.

(ii) **Concentration conservatism (remaining factor):** *The remaining gap after pointwise correction is attributable to conservative concentration tools for structured random designs. Entry-wise Bernstein and global fourth-moment bounds treat $\psi_j(x_i)\psi_k(x_i)$ as generic bounded variables, ignoring structural cancellations and anti-concentration. This motivates the small-ball route in Corollary 19.*

Quantitative evidence for Bernstein conservatism: *To verify that the Bernstein bound is indeed the source of conservatism, we conducted the following numerical experiment: for fixed design matrix dimensions ($s = 5$, $D = 100$), we generated 10^4 independent realizations of the empirical Gram matrix $\widehat{\Sigma}_{S^*}$ with sample sizes $N \in \{100, 200, 500, 1000\}$. We computed:*

1. *The actual maximum deviation $\|\widehat{\Sigma}_{S^*} - \Sigma_{S^*}\|_{\max}$ across all entries.*

2. *The Bernstein prediction for this deviation at confidence level $\delta = 0.05$: $t_{\text{Bernstein}} = \sqrt{\frac{2L^2 \log(2s^2/\delta)}{N}} + \frac{2L \log(2s^2/\delta)}{3N}$.*

The ratio $t_{\text{Bernstein}}/\text{actual deviation}$ averaged 15–30 \times across experimental conditions, confirming that the Bernstein bound is conservative by one to two orders of magnitude for this structured dictionary. This conservatism directly translates to the N requirement: since $N \sim t^{-2}$ for achieving the same RE tolerance, a 15 \times larger t requires 225 \times more samples. Combined with the s^2 union bound overhead (factor ~ 25 for $s = 5$), this explains the bulk of the remaining 10^4 – 10^5 gap.

This type of constant gap is well-documented in the sparse recovery literature: Wainwright’s [33] sharp LASSO analysis requires $N \gtrsim s \log D$, whereas empirical phase-transition studies in related sparse-recovery models (including AMP/BP analyses) often follow $N = O(s \log(D/s))$ with substantially smaller constants [13]. Even larger gaps can appear in the ultra-coherent regime $\mu \rightarrow 1$.

Interpretation: *The theory functions as a **scaling descriptor**: it reveals that the fundamental cost of ultra-coherent recovery is controlled by κ_{pop}^{-4} . The absolute constant in the sufficient bound is a proof artifact, while the geometric role of κ_{pop} is robust. The conditional small-ball theorem provides a principled route from conservative worst-case constants toward practically relevant linear-in- s scaling.*

Remark 29 (Testable Predictions of the κ_{pop}^{-4} Scaling Law). *Despite the conservative absolute constant, the κ_{pop}^{-4} scaling law makes several testable qualitative predictions that are consistent with our experiments:*

1. **κ_{pop}^{-4} scaling with grid spacing:** *Since $\kappa_{\text{pop}} \sim K^{-(\alpha+\beta/2+1/2)}$ depends on K and the grid spacing $\Delta\alpha$ enters through $\Delta \sim \epsilon_{\min}(\Delta\alpha)^2$, Theorem 18 predicts $N_{\text{crit}} \sim (\Delta\alpha)^{-4}$ at fixed K . This is validated empirically (Section 3), with the fine grid ($\Delta\alpha = 0.02$) requiring $\sim 14\times$ more samples than the coarse grid ($\Delta\alpha = 0.1$), consistent with $(0.1/0.02)^4/\text{const} \approx 625/\text{const}$ order of magnitude.*
2. **Algorithm comparison:** *LASSO outperforms OMP in high-coherence regimes, consistent with the RE-based analysis (OMP requires the exact recovery condition which fails when $\mu \rightarrow 1$).*
3. **Phase transition existence:** *There exists a sharp transition between “coarse grid failure” and “near-oracle success,” governed by the SSC gap Δ , confirmed by the sigmoidal recovery curves.*
4. **Bottleneck identification:** *The concentration condition (not the SSC condition) is the binding constraint for moderate s , consistent with the theoretical prediction that the first sample complexity term dominates when $s^2/\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4 \gg \sigma^2 \log D/\Delta^2$.*

Thus, the theory serves as a **scaling law**: it identifies which parameters control difficulty (κ_{pop} , s , $\Delta\alpha$) and how they interact ($N \sim \kappa^{-4}$), even though the universal constant is conservative for specific instances. The qualitative consistency between these predictions and the experiments supports the scaling structure, though fully validating the κ^{-4} exponent would require systematic experiments across a wider range of (α, β, K, s) configurations, which we leave for future work.

Remark 30 (Toward instance-optimal bounds). The 10^7 – 10^8 theory-practice gap arises partly from using uniform worst-case bounds. An **instance-optimal** analysis, using the pointwise separation $\kappa(\alpha^*)$ at the true exponent rather than the uniform κ_{pop} , would yield tighter predictions. For a specific instance with true exponent α^* :

$$N_{\text{instance}} \gtrsim \frac{s}{\kappa(\alpha^*)^4} \approx \frac{s}{(21.76 \cdot \kappa_{\text{pop}})^4} \approx \frac{N_{\text{uniform}}}{2.2 \times 10^5}, \quad (24)$$

reducing the gap by roughly five orders of magnitude.

However, instance-optimal bounds require a priori knowledge of α^* (to compute $\kappa(\alpha^*)$), which is circular: we do not know α^* before detection. A practical compromise is:

1. **Pilot estimation**: Use a small N_{pilot} to estimate $\hat{\alpha} \approx \alpha^*$.
2. **Adaptive bound**: Compute $\kappa(\hat{\alpha})$ and predict the full sample size $N_{\text{full}} \gtrsim s/\kappa(\hat{\alpha})^4$ under the small-ball route.

The pilot phase succeeds with $N_{\text{pilot}} \ll N_{\text{full}}$ because coarse detection requires fewer samples than fine coefficient estimation. Formalizing this adaptive procedure, and proving that the pilot error $|\hat{\alpha} - \alpha^*|$ does not catastrophically affect sample complexity, is an important direction for making the theory more algorithmically prescribable.

Remark 31 (Nonconvex alternatives and reweighted ℓ_1). Our analysis focuses on the standard ℓ_1 -penalized LASSO, but nonconvex penalties such as SCAD [16] and MCP [36] are natural alternatives in high-coherence regimes. For incoherent designs, these penalties achieve minimax-optimal rates with weaker signal strength requirements. In our ultra-coherent setting, two benefits are plausible:

1. **Reduced bias**: Nonconvex penalties avoid the $O(\lambda_N)$ shrinkage bias of LASSO, potentially improving coefficient estimation accuracy for the singular atom.
2. **Weaker signal requirements**: The s^2 factor gap between our sufficient condition ($N \gtrsim s^2 \kappa_{\text{pop}}^{-4}$) and the information-theoretic lower bound ($N \gtrsim \kappa_{\text{pop}}^{-4}$) may be partially attributable to the LASSO analysis; nonconvex penalties or reweighted ℓ_1 methods [8] could reduce this factor.

However, the support-block RE condition (Theorem 8) is penalty-agnostic: the geometric quantity κ_{pop} controls the problem difficulty regardless of the optimization method. Systematically comparing LASSO, SCAD/MCP, and reweighted ℓ_1 in the ultra-coherent regime is an important empirical direction that we leave to future work.

Remark 32 (Computational complexity). The LASSO problem with D atoms and N observations is solved via coordinate descent in $O(ND)$ operations per iteration, with typically $O(\log(1/\epsilon))$ iterations for ϵ -accuracy. For our setting ($D = 24$, $N \leq 10^3$), each solve takes < 1 second on a standard laptop. The computational bottleneck in practice is the dictionary construction (Gram–Schmidt orthonormalization, $O(K^2N)$), not the optimization. For larger-scale applications ($D \sim 10^3$, $N \sim 10^5$), specialized solvers (e.g., ADMM or proximal gradient) should be used; the per-iteration cost remains $O(ND)$.

Remark 33 (Noise model assumptions). Our theoretical results assume i.i.d. sub-Gaussian observation noise. In the motivating applications (FEM solutions with corner singularities, fracture mechanics), discretization errors are typically structured: spatially correlated, non-stationary, and with distribution depending on mesh refinement. The sub-Gaussian assumption is most realistic when noise arises from measurement uncertainty rather than discretization error. For structured noise, the Bernstein concentration bounds can be replaced by mixing-type inequalities (if spatial correlation decays) or by directly bounding the empirical process supremum; the κ_{pop}^{-4} scaling is expected to persist, with modified constants.

N	LASSO Singular	OMP Singular	LASSO Full	OMP Full
8	1.00	0.80	0.00	0.00
12	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00
24	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00
60	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00
144	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00
420	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00

Table 2

Core sparse-recovery benchmark from `sparse_recovery_core_summary.json`. Singular detection is easy; exact support recovery is not.

3. Numerical Experiments

3.1. Protocol and Reproducibility

All reported values are produced by scripts in `experiments_clean/src/mathproject/experiments/` and written to `experiments_clean/results/`. For the core sparse-recovery experiment we use `sparse_recovery_core_summary.json` and `sparse_recovery_core_curve.csv`:

- Sampling: $x \sim \mu$ on $[0, 1]$ with CDF $F(x) = x^{\beta_{\text{mass}}}$ and $\beta_{\text{mass}} = 0.55$.
- Dictionary: $D = 24$ atoms, true sparsity $s = 5$, true singular exponent $\alpha^* = 0.35$.
- Noise: Gaussian with $\sigma = 0.006$ (stress tests also use $\sigma = 0.02$).
- Normalization: each design column is divided by empirical RMS before fitting.
- Regularization: $\lambda_N = 4\sigma\sqrt{2\log(D)/N}$.
- Selection threshold: coefficient magnitude > 0.03 .

The same files also report $\mu(D)$, SSC gap, and empirical RE diagnostics used below.

3.2. Core Sparse-Recovery Result

For the baseline instance ($D = 24$, $s = 5$, $\alpha^* = 0.35$), the diagnostics are:

$$\mu(D) = 0.9974139, \quad \Delta_{\text{SSC}} = 0.0160503, \quad \hat{\kappa}_{\text{RE}} = 0.0263922.$$

LASSO detects the singular atom with rate 1.00 for every tested $N \in \{8, 12, 17, 24, 36, 60, 96, 144, 216, 312, 420\}$. OMP reaches 0.80 at $N = 8$ and 1.00 for $N \geq 12$ in the same benchmark. In contrast, full support recovery remains near 0 for both methods, matching the detection-vs-recovery distinction in Remark 20.

3.3. Small-Ball Validation and Fourth-Moment Bottleneck

We report dedicated diagnostics for the normalized Jacobi regime $K = s$ using `run_full_validation_protocol.py` and `compute_small_ball_sweep.py`. The purpose of this subsection is to evaluate the conditional assumptions in Corollary 19 and to compare anti-concentration with fourth-moment scaling in a common protocol.

Support-block small-ball estimate at $s = 20$. For a support-block containing one singular atom ($\alpha^* = 0.35$) and $s - 1$ smooth Jacobi atoms, we estimate

$$\lambda_{\min}(\Sigma) \approx 0.8184, \quad p_0 := \inf_{\|v\|_2=1} \mathbb{P}(|\langle v, X \rangle| \geq 0.1) \approx 0.781.$$

The spherical infimum is approximated over random directions plus extremal fourth-moment eigen-directions. This is evidence for the assumption, not an analytic lower bound.

Parameter sweep for (p_0, u_0) . Using `validation_outputs/small_ball_sweep_support_block.csv`, we compute finite-direction lower bounds

$$\hat{p}_0(u_0, s) := \min_{v \in \mathcal{V}} \mathbb{P}(|\langle v, X \rangle| \geq u_0),$$

with \mathcal{V} containing 303 directions (300 random unit vectors and 3 extremal fourth-moment eigen-directions). Results:

s	$u_0 = 0.05$	$u_0 = 0.10$	$u_0 = 0.20$
5	0.8008	0.7272	0.5356
10	0.7914	0.6057	0.4838
20	0.8632	0.7191	0.5814
50	0.7493	0.4277	0.1395

Across this grid, $\hat{\rho}_0(u_0, s)$ remains above 0.1 (Figure 2). We emphasize that these are finite-sample directional proxies; confidence bands and broader sweeps are left for future work.

Figure 1: Support-block small-ball sweep in the Jacobi $K = s$ ensemble. Curves show empirical lower bounds $\hat{\rho}_0(u_0, s)$ for $u_0 \in \{0.05, 0.10, 0.20\}$.

Fourth-moment operator growth. With corrected normalization, the operator norm of $\mathbf{B}_{jk} = \mathbb{E}[\psi_j^2 \psi_k^2]$ over $s \in \{5, 10, 20, 50\}$ is:

s	$\ \mathbf{B}\ _{\text{op}}$
5	1.29×10^1
10	4.17×10^1
20	1.35×10^2
50	8.40×10^2

The log-log slope is 1.809, substantially above linear growth.

Comparison with phase-threshold envelope. In the same validation suite (`validation_outputs/tier3_phase_transition.csv`), the tested envelope over $N/s \in \{1, 1.5, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12\}$ is $N_{\text{crit}} = 12s$ on $s \in \{5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 50\}$. This should be interpreted as a finite-grid upper envelope because the 90% criterion is not reached in every case within the tested grid. On that grid, it is nonetheless inconsistent with $s^{1.809}$ scaling (Figure 3).

Phase-collapse diagnostic on $N/(s \log s)$. We export detection-rate curves by sparsity (`validation_outputs/tier3_phase_curve_by_s.csv`; script: `compute_phase_collapse.py`) and plot them against $N/(s \log s)$ in `figure_phase_collapse_slog.pdf`. At the current trial budget, these curves remain noisy and do not show a sharp universal collapse. We therefore treat this figure as a diagnostic, not as a formal scaling claim.

Instance-specific separation. For the same protocol, we obtain

$$\kappa_{\text{pop}} \approx 0.0211, \quad \kappa_{\text{point}}(0.35) \approx 0.4590, \quad \frac{\kappa_{\text{point}}(0.35)}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}} \approx 21.76.$$

Figure 2: Tier-3 phase-threshold envelope versus reference exponents. The observed envelope is linear on the tested grid, while the fourth-moment reference grows as $s^{1.809}$.

This quantifies the gap between uniform and pointwise separation discussed in Remarks 28 and 30.

3.4. SSC Diagnostics and Applicability

Train and test diagnostics (`recovery_delta_small_n_audit.csv`, 60 trials per cell, fresh test set size 1000) separate two regimes:

- SSC positive cells ($\Delta_{SSC} > 0$): mean LASSO singular recovery 0.9764 at $\sigma = 0.006$.
- SSC nonpositive cells ($\Delta_{SSC} \leq 0$): mean LASSO singular recovery 0.6958 at $\sigma = 0.006$.

For the concrete non-SSC case $c_{sing} = 0.8$ ($\Delta_{SSC} \approx -0.00796$), recovery rises from 0.60 ($N = 8$) to 0.9167 ($N = 60$). For $c_{sing} = 1.4$ ($\Delta_{SSC} \approx 0.01605$), recovery is 1.00 for $N \in \{8, 12, 24, 60\}$. These results support the paper’s interpretation: SSC is sufficient and informative, but not necessary.

3.5. Grid Resolution and Oracle Ablation

Oracle-ablation diagnostics (`recovery_oracle_ablation_audit.csv`) quantify discretization effects:

- Coarse exponent grid $\{0.1, 0.2, \dots, 0.9\}$: closest exponent recovery remains low, between 0.233 and 0.333 for $N \in \{8, 12, 24, 60\}$.
- Near-oracle pair $\{0.34, 0.36\}$ around $\alpha^* = 0.35$: closest-exponent recovery is 1.00 for $N \in \{8, 12, 24, 60\}$.

This clarifies that the quality of the exponent grid can dominate downstream sparse selection performance.

3.6. Systematic Parameter Sweeps

We ran systematic sweeps over sparsity, gap size, weight exponent, and singular exponent. The summary files are:

- `focm_scaling_summary.json`
- `focm_completion_summary.json`
- `focm_scaling_s_summary.csv`
- `focm_scaling_delta_summary.csv`

- focm_beta_kappa_summary.csv
- focm_alpha_endpoint_stability_1d.csv

For the sparsity sweep ($s \in \{3, 5, 7, 9, 11\}$), the empirical threshold for 95% detection is

$$N_{\min}^{0.95} = \{8, 12, 16, 72, 144\}.$$

The log log fit of N_{\min} against s has slope 2.33 and $R^2 = 0.89$.

For the gap sweep, the log log fit of N_{\min} against Δ^{-2} has slope 1.29 and $R^2 = 0.81$. This is consistent with monotone growth in sample demand as the singular correlation gap decreases.

For the weight sweep $\beta_{\text{mass}} \in \{0.35, 0.45, 0.55, 0.70, 0.85, 1.00, 1.20\}$, the projection based separation estimate decreases from 1.96×10^{-2} to 2.68×10^{-3} . Over the same range, κ^{-4} increases from 6.78×10^6 to 1.93×10^{10} , and the observed threshold moves from $N_{\min} = 8$ to $N_{\min} = 216$ before the strict 90% criterion becomes unresolved at the largest β_{mass} values.

For the exponent sweep $\alpha \in \{0.05, 0.10, 0.20, 0.35, 0.50, 0.70, 0.90, 0.95\}$, the one dimensional matched degree gain remains large across the full range, from about 8.26×10^3 to 4.82×10^6 , while absolute discovery error remains small in the interior and increases near the endpoint.

3.7. Fixed-Parameter Degree Sweep in K

To isolate degree sensitivity, we ran a fixed-parameter sweep with

$$\alpha = 0.35, \quad \beta_{\text{mass}} = 0.55, \quad s = 5, \quad \sigma = 0.05, \quad K \in \{4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16\}.$$

The outputs are:

- k_degree_phase_transition_curve.csv
- k_degree_phase_transition_summary.csv
- k_degree_phase_transition_summary.json

Three quantitative trends are stable across this sweep. First, the dictionary coherence increases from 0.9974 at $K = 4$ to 0.9995 at $K = 16$. Second, the empirical polynomial envelope grows from $L_{\text{poly}} \approx 3.94$ to $L_{\text{poly}} \approx 7.67$, while the theoretical growth proxy $K^{2\tau}$ with $\tau = \beta + 1/2$ increases from 18.38 to 337.79. Third, the strict detection threshold $N_{\min}^{0.99}$ moves from 8 to 12 at degrees $K = 8$ and $K = 14$, and the recovery rate at $N = 8$ drops to 0.975 and 0.925 at those two degrees.

The degree effect is therefore visible at the edge of the phase transition even when average detection remains high. This is consistent with the theory that increasing K tightens geometric separation and inflates envelope driven concentration constants.

3.8. Matched-DOF Baselines and Discovery

Matched-DOF approximation results (matched_dof_comparison_summary.json) at $\text{DOF} = 10$ give:

$$e_{\text{smooth}} = 1.4083 \times 10^{-3}, \quad e_{\text{aug}} = 2.5006 \times 10^{-8}, \quad e_{\text{weighted}} = 7.0115 \times 10^{-5}, \quad e_{\text{rational}} = 2.1755 \times 10^{-5}.$$

At mismatch $|\Delta\alpha| = 0.05$, error is 4.2163×10^{-5} , still a 33.4× gain over smooth at matched DOF.

Blind discovery (exponent_discovery_summary.json) is accurate in 1D for low noise: mean $|\hat{\alpha} - \alpha^*| = 0$ for $\sigma \in \{0, 10^{-4}\}$ and 0.006 at $\sigma = 10^{-3}$. At $\sigma = 5 \times 10^{-3}$, mean error increases to 0.031. In 2D, the same script reports larger bias (mean recovered $\alpha \approx 0.54$ – 0.553 for true $\alpha^* = 0.5$), so we treat the 2D discovery stage as preliminary.

3.9. 2D Corner Bridge and Extended Suites

For the manufactured Poisson corner benchmark (poisson2d_corner_summary.json), degree 10 gives

$$\|e_{\text{corner}}^{\text{smooth}}\|_{L^2} = 7.3512 \times 10^{-3}, \quad \|e_{\text{corner}}^{\text{aug}}\|_{L^2} = 1.1535 \times 10^{-4},$$

a local gain factor of 63.73×; global L^2 decreases from 9.5077×10^{-4} to 3.3941×10^{-5} (Table ??).

Large suite artifacts are:

Degree	Smooth corner L^2	Augmented corner L^2	Gain
8	8.4869×10^{-3}	1.0517×10^{-3}	8.07×
9	7.3738×10^{-3}	1.3863×10^{-4}	53.19×
10	7.3512×10^{-3}	1.1535×10^{-4}	63.73×
11	6.9239×10^{-3}	9.3970×10^{-5}	73.68×
12	6.8396×10^{-3}	4.3012×10^{-5}	159.01×

Table 3

2D corner benchmark summary from `poisson2d_corner_summary.json`.

- `level1_validation_summary.json`
- `multilevel_evidence_summary.json`
- `critical_scaling_suite_summary.json`

They are directionally consistent with the main claims, but finite-size exponents are noisy. The current finite-size fit reports slope 3.87 with a wide 95% interval $[-8.05, 15.79]$, so we avoid strong exponent claims from this block.

3.10. How $\kappa_{\text{point}}(\alpha)$ is Computed in Practice

For a fixed α , we estimate

$$\kappa_{\text{point}}(\alpha) = \inf_{p \in P_K} \|\psi_\alpha - p\|_{L^2(\mu)}$$

numerically by least-squares projection of x^α onto the degree- K polynomial span on a dense quadrature grid sampled under μ . The residual $L^2(\mu)$ norm is the reported estimate. In the codebase this is implemented in the diagnostic utilities and is distinct from the support-block RE diagnostic $\hat{\kappa}_{\text{RE}}$ reported in `sparse_recovery_core_summary.json`.

Data Availability. All experiments used Python (NumPy, SciPy, scikit-learn). Code and data are in https://anonymous.4open.science/r/experiments_clean-3E20/. Key outputs include recovery statistics, phase transitions, and scaling analyses (JSON/CSV). See `README.md`.

4. Conclusion

The main conclusion is that κ_{pop} is the intrinsic geometric complexity parameter for this class of singular dictionaries. The central implication chain is

$$\kappa_{\text{pop}} \implies \lambda_{\min}(\Sigma_{S^*}) \implies \lambda_{\min}(\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*}) \implies \text{reliable singular atom selection.}$$

This route separates geometric identifiability from optimization details and explains why global mutual coherence is not the right complexity parameter in this regime.

At the finite-sample level, the rigorous entry-wise route remains conservative and yields $N \gtrsim s^2 \kappa_{\text{pop}}^{-4} \log D$. The conditional small-ball route gives $N \gtrsim s \log(s/\delta)/(p_0 u_0^2 \kappa_{\text{pop}}^4)$, which is linear in s up to logarithms when (p_0, u_0) are bounded away from zero.

Numerically, we observe $p_0 \approx 0.781$ at $u_0 = 0.1$, $s = 20$, together with a fourth-moment growth diagnostic $\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}} \sim s^{1.809}$ in the normalized $K = s$ protocol. This supports the interpretation that anti-concentration, rather than fourth-moment closure, is the relevant mechanism for improved s -dependence in this ensemble.

Three directions are central for future work. First, prove uniform small-ball constants analytically in the Jacobi $K \sim s$ regime. Second, derive sharper non-asymptotic bounds that use pointwise separation $\kappa(\alpha^*)$. Third, extend the framework to multiple singular atoms and to basis construction under estimated sampling measures.

A. Proofs of Main Results

A.1. Appendix A: Weighted Müntz–Szász Separation

A.1.1. Setup and Notation

Define the weighted L^2 space:

$$L^2_\beta := L^2([0, 1], x^\beta dx), \quad \|f\|_\beta^2 = \int_0^1 |f(x)|^2 x^\beta dx. \quad (25)$$

A.1.2. Quoted Theorem

Theorem 34 (Quoted Weighted Endpoint Approximation Rate). *Let $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and $\beta > -1$. For $P_K = \text{span}\{x^k : 0 \leq k \leq K\}$,*

$$c_1(\alpha, \beta) K^{-(\alpha+\beta/2+1/2)} \leq \inf_{p \in P_K} \|x^\alpha - p\|_{L^2_\beta} \leq c_2(\alpha, \beta) K^{-(\alpha+\beta/2+1/2)}, \quad (26)$$

where $c_1(\alpha, \beta), c_2(\alpha, \beta) > 0$ do not depend on K .

Reference note. We use this as a quoted approximation-theoretic input. The endpoint-singularity rate follows from classical weighted polynomial approximation results and Jacobi endpoint asymptotics (see, e.g., [5, 26]). In this paper we only need the lower bound constant $c_1(\alpha, \beta)$.

A.1.3. Norm Comparison Lemma

Lemma 35 (Transfer from L^2_β to $L^2(\mu)$). *Under Assumption 1, for any $f \in L^2([0, 1])$,*

$$\|f\|_{L^2(\mu)}^2 \geq c_0 \int_0^\delta |f(x)|^2 x^\beta dx. \quad (27)$$

Proof. By definition,

$$\|f\|_{L^2(\mu)}^2 = \int_0^1 |f(x)|^2 w(x) dx \geq \int_0^\delta |f(x)|^2 w(x) dx \geq c_0 \int_0^\delta |f(x)|^2 x^\beta dx, \quad (28)$$

using $w(x) \geq c_0 x^\beta$ on $(0, \delta]$. □

A.1.4. Normalization Bound

Lemma 36 (Upper bound on $\|x^\alpha\|_{L^2(\mu)}$). *Under Assumption 1,*

$$\|x^\alpha\|_{L^2(\mu)}^2 \leq \frac{\|w\|_{L^\infty}}{2\alpha + 1}. \quad (29)$$

Proof.

$$\|x^\alpha\|_{L^2(\mu)}^2 = \int_0^1 x^{2\alpha} w(x) dx \leq \|w\|_{L^\infty} \int_0^1 x^{2\alpha} dx = \frac{\|w\|_{L^\infty}}{2\alpha + 1}. \quad (30)$$

□

A.1.5. Proof of Lemma 4

Proof. Let $\psi_1(x) = x^\alpha / \|x^\alpha\|_{L^2(\mu)}$. For any $p \in P_K$,

$$\|\psi_1 - p\|_{L^2(\mu)}^2 = \int_0^1 \left| \frac{x^\alpha}{\|x^\alpha\|_{L^2(\mu)}} - p(x) \right|^2 w(x) dx \quad (31)$$

$$\geq c_0 \int_0^\delta \left| \frac{x^\alpha}{\|x^\alpha\|_{L^2(\mu)}} - p(x) \right|^2 x^\beta dx \quad (\text{by Lemma 35}) \quad (32)$$

$$= \frac{c_0}{\|x^\alpha\|_{L^2(\mu)}^2} \int_0^\delta |x^\alpha - \tilde{p}(x)|^2 x^\beta dx, \quad (33)$$

where $\tilde{p}(x) = \|x^\alpha\|_{L^2(\mu)} p(x) \in P_K$.

By Theorem 34,

$$\inf_{q \in P_K} \int_0^1 |x^\alpha - q(x)|^2 x^\beta dx \geq [c_1(\alpha, \beta) K^{-(\alpha+\beta/2+1/2)}]^2. \quad (34)$$

Rescaling argument: We now bound $\int_0^\delta |x^\alpha - \tilde{p}(x)|^2 x^\beta dx$ from below. Substitute $x = \delta t$, $t \in [0, 1]$:

$$\int_0^\delta |x^\alpha - \tilde{p}(x)|^2 x^\beta dx = \delta^{2\alpha+\beta+1} \int_0^1 |t^\alpha - \delta^{-\alpha} \tilde{p}(\delta t)|^2 t^\beta dt. \quad (35)$$

Define $\tilde{p}_\delta(t) := \delta^{-\alpha} \tilde{p}(\delta t)$. Since $\tilde{p}(x) = \sum_{k=0}^K a_k x^k$, we have $\tilde{p}_\delta(t) = \sum_{k=0}^K a_k \delta^{k-\alpha} t^k$, which is again a polynomial of degree $\leq K$ in t .

Crucially, the coefficient map $\{a_k\}_{k=0}^K \mapsto \{a_k \delta^{k-\alpha}\}_{k=0}^K$ is a bijection on \mathbb{R}^{K+1} (since $\delta > 0$). Therefore, as \tilde{p} ranges over all of P_K , so does \tilde{p}_δ . This yields:

$$\inf_{\tilde{p} \in P_K} \int_0^\delta |x^\alpha - \tilde{p}(x)|^2 x^\beta dx = \delta^{2\alpha+\beta+1} \inf_{q \in P_K} \int_0^1 |t^\alpha - q(t)|^2 t^\beta dt \geq \delta^{2\alpha+\beta+1} [c_1(\alpha, \beta) K^{-(\alpha+\beta/2+1/2)}]^2. \quad (36)$$

Choice of δ and constant non-sharpness: The factor $\delta^{2\alpha+\beta+1} < 1$ (for $\delta \in (0, 1)$) makes the lower bound smaller than the $[0, 1]$ -global bound. However:

1. For any fixed $\delta > 0$, the lower bound is strictly positive and explicit.
2. The optimal choice $\delta = 1$ (full interval) is not available because Lemma 35 only provides the lower bound $w(x) \geq c_0 x^\beta$ on $[0, \delta]$, where δ is the Assumption 1 parameter.
3. We absorb the factor $\delta^{2\alpha+\beta+1}$ into the overall constant $C(\alpha, \beta, c_0, \delta, \|w\|_{L^\infty})$ defined below. The parameter δ is fixed by the weight function w and does not depend on K , so the *rate* $K^{-(\alpha+\beta/2+1/2)}$ is unaffected; only the prefactor changes.
4. **Quantitative impact:** For the experimental parameters ($\beta = 0.55$, $\delta \approx 0.5$), the prefactor reduction is $\delta^{2\alpha+\beta+1} \approx 0.5^{2.25} \approx 0.21$, i.e., approximately a factor of 5 in the squared constant. This is moderate and does not qualitatively change the scaling.

The resulting constant is *explicit but non-sharp*: it provides a rigorous lower bound, but the actual separation may be larger (as observed in experiments where pointwise κ exceeds the uniform bound).

Combining with Lemma 36:

$$\|\psi_1 - p\|_{L^2(\mu)}^2 \geq \frac{c_0}{\|x^\alpha\|_{L^2(\mu)}^2} \cdot \delta^{2\alpha+\beta+1} [c_1(\alpha, \beta) K^{-(\alpha+\beta/2+1/2)}]^2 \geq \frac{c_0(2\alpha+1)}{\|w\|_{L^\infty}} \cdot \delta^{2\alpha+\beta+1} [c_1(\alpha, \beta)]^2 K^{-2(\alpha+\beta/2+1/2)}. \quad (37)$$

Taking infimum over p and square root:

$$\kappa_{\text{pop}} \geq C(\alpha, \beta, c_0, \delta, \|w\|_{L^\infty}) K^{-(\alpha+\beta/2+1/2)}, \quad (38)$$

where the constant is fully explicit:

$$C(\alpha, \beta, c_0, \delta, \|w\|_{L^\infty}) = c_1(\alpha, \beta) \sqrt{\frac{c_0(2\alpha+1)}{\|w\|_{L^\infty}}} \delta^{\alpha+(\beta+1)/2}. \quad (39)$$

That is, once the quoted approximation constant $c_1(\alpha, \beta)$ is fixed, the transfer to $L^2(\mu)$ introduces only the explicit multiplicative factor above. \square

A.2. Appendix B: Restricted Eigenvalue Condition

A.2.1. Block Decomposition

Let $S^* = \{1\} \cup S_{\text{smooth}}$ with $|S^*| = s$. Write

$$\Sigma = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \rho^\top \\ \rho & \Sigma_{\text{smooth}} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (40)$$

where $\rho \in \mathbb{R}^{s-1}$ with $\rho_j = \langle \psi_1, \psi_{k_j} \rangle_{L^2(\mu)}$ for $k_j \in S_{\text{smooth}}$.

A.2.2. Friedrichs Angle

Definition 37 (Friedrichs angle).

$$\cos \theta_{\alpha, K} = \sup_{u \in P_K \setminus \{0\}} \frac{|\langle \psi_1, u \rangle_{L^2(\mu)}|}{\|\psi_1\|_{L^2(\mu)} \|u\|_{L^2(\mu)}}. \quad (41)$$

Lemma 38 (Sine bound via Müntz–Szász).

$$\sin \theta_{\alpha, K} = \sqrt{1 - \cos^2 \theta_{\alpha, K}} \geq \kappa_{\text{pop}}. \quad (42)$$

Proof. Let $p^* = \text{proj}_{P_K} \psi_1$ be the orthogonal projection of ψ_1 onto P_K in $L^2(\mu)$. Since P_K is a closed subspace, the projection exists and satisfies $\psi_1 - p^* \perp P_K$. By the Pythagorean theorem in $L^2(\mu)$:

$$1 = \|\psi_1\|^2 = \|\psi_1 - p^*\|^2 + \|p^*\|^2. \quad (43)$$

The projection norm is the cosine of the Friedrichs angle:

$$\|p^*\| = \sup_{u \in P_K, \|u\|=1} |\langle \psi_1, u \rangle| = \cos \theta_{\alpha, K}. \quad (44)$$

Therefore $\sin \theta_{\alpha, K} = \sqrt{1 - \|p^*\|^2} = \|\psi_1 - p^*\|$.

Now, $\|\psi_1 - p^*\| = \inf_{q \in P_K} \|\psi_1 - q\| = \kappa_{\text{pop}}$ by the projection characterization of best approximation. Hence $\sin \theta_{\alpha, K} = \kappa_{\text{pop}}$. \square

A.2.3. Correlation Vector Bound

Lemma 39 (Bound on $\|\rho\|_2$ via Bessel's inequality). *Under Assumption 2 (orthonormal smooth atoms), the correlation vector $\rho \in \mathbb{R}^{s-1}$ satisfies the s -independent bound*

$$\|\rho\|_2^2 \leq 1 - \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2. \quad (45)$$

Equivalently, $\|\rho\|_2 \leq \cos \theta_{\alpha, K} = \sqrt{1 - \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2}$.

Proof. Assumptions and preliminaries: This proof relies on two key assumptions:

1. **Orthonormality:** The smooth atoms $\{\psi_{k_j}\}_{j=1}^{s-1}$ are orthonormal in $L^2(\mu)$ (Assumption 2).
2. **Subspace inclusion:** Each $\psi_{k_j} \in P_K$, which implies $\text{span}\{\psi_{k_j}\} \subseteq P_K$.

Assumption 2 is satisfied exactly when using orthonormal polynomials (e.g., shifted Jacobi polynomials) as the smooth basis. For empirical orthonormalization (Remark 6), the inclusion holds only approximately: if $\tilde{\psi}_{k_j} = \psi_{k_j} + e_j$ where $\|e_j\|_{L^2(\mu)} \leq \epsilon_{\text{orth}}$, then the error in the bound is $O(s\epsilon_{\text{orth}})$, which is negligible when $\epsilon_{\text{orth}} \ll 1/s$.

Main argument: By Bessel's inequality,

$$\|\rho\|_2^2 = \sum_{j=1}^{s-1} |\langle \psi_1, \psi_{k_j} \rangle_{L^2(\mu)}|^2 \leq \|\text{proj}_{\text{span}\{\psi_{k_j}\}} \psi_1\|_{L^2(\mu)}^2 \leq \|\text{proj}_{P_K} \psi_1\|_{L^2(\mu)}^2 = \cos^2 \theta_{\alpha, K} = 1 - \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2, \quad (46)$$

where the second inequality uses the subspace inclusion, and the last equality follows from Lemma 38.

Remark 40 (Comparison with the naive bound). *The entry-wise bound $|\rho_j| \leq \sqrt{1 - \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2}$ combined with $s - 1$ terms gives $(s - 1)(1 - \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2)$, which grows with s and restricts Theorem 8 to $s = O(1)$. Bessel’s inequality avoids this by exploiting the orthonormality of the smooth atoms: the projections $\langle \psi_1, \psi_{k_j} \rangle$ share the same “budget” $\|\text{proj}_{P_K} \psi_1\|_2^2$, so adding more orthonormal atoms does not increase $\|\rho\|_2^2$.* □

A.2.4. Proof of Theorem 8

Proof. We prove the two claims separately.

Part 1: Minimum eigenvalue of Σ_{S^*} .

By Assumption 2, $\Sigma_{\text{smooth}} = I_{s-1}$, so

$$\Sigma_{S^*} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \rho^\top \\ \rho & I_{s-1} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (47)$$

The Schur complement of the (1, 1) block is $I_{s-1} - \rho\rho^\top / (1) = I_{s-1} - \rho\rho^\top$, and the Schur complement of the lower-right block is $1 - \rho^\top I_{s-1}^{-1} \rho = 1 - \|\rho\|_2^2$.

For the eigenvalues: decompose $\mathbb{R}^{s-1} = \text{span}\{\rho\} \oplus \ker(\rho^\top)$. On $\ker(\rho^\top)$ (dimension $s - 2$), Σ_{S^*} acts as $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & I \end{pmatrix}$, giving eigenvalue 1 with multiplicity $s - 2$. On $\text{span}\{e_1, \rho/\|\rho\|_2\}$ (dimension 2), Σ_{S^*} reduces to $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & \|\rho\|_2 \\ \|\rho\|_2 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$, with eigenvalues $1 \pm \|\rho\|_2$.

By Lemma 39, $\|\rho\|_2 \leq \sqrt{1 - \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2}$. Therefore

$$\lambda_{\min}(\Sigma_{S^*}) = 1 - \|\rho\|_2 \geq 1 - \sqrt{1 - \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2}. \quad (48)$$

To obtain the simpler bound: for $x = \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2 \in [0, 1]$,

$$1 - \sqrt{1 - x} = \frac{x}{1 + \sqrt{1 - x}} \geq \frac{x}{2}, \quad (49)$$

since $1 + \sqrt{1 - x} \leq 2$. Hence $\lambda_{\min}(\Sigma_{S^*}) \geq \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2 / 2$.

Part 2: Support-block RE suffices; full cone RE is not needed.

The standard LASSO analysis establishes the RE condition on the cone $C(S^*, 3) = \{v : \|v_{(S^*)^c}\|_1 \leq 3\|v_{S^*}\|_1\}$. In our ultra-coherent setting, the full cone RE *does not hold* via generic coherence-based arguments (see Remark 41 below). Our key observation is that the primal-dual witness (PDW) construction *bypasses* the full cone RE entirely: it only requires the support-block RE from Part 1, combined with separate off-support control via the SSC (Lemma 47).

Step 1 (Support-block RE): From Part 1,

$$\lambda_{\min}(\Sigma_{S^*}) \geq \frac{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2}{2},$$

which is a property of the $s \times s$ Gram submatrix on the true support only.

Step 2 (Empirical concentration): By Lemma 9, with probability $\geq 1 - \delta$,

$$\lambda_{\min}(\widehat{\Sigma}_{S^*}) \geq \frac{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2}{4},$$

provided $N \gtrsim s^2 \log(s/\delta) / \kappa_{\text{pop}}^4$.

Step 3 (Restricted LASSO error): Consider the *oracle restricted problem*: the LASSO estimator restricted to the support S^* (with off-support coefficients set to zero). The standard analysis (Bühlmann–van de Geer 2011, Theorem 6.1) gives:

$$\|\tilde{c}_{S^*} - c_{S^*}^*\|_2 \leq \frac{4\sqrt{s}\lambda_N}{\lambda_{\min}(\widehat{\Sigma}_{S^*})} \leq \frac{16\sqrt{s}\lambda_N}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2}.$$

This bound uses *only* the support-block minimum eigenvalue, not any property of Σ restricted to the full cone.

Step 4 (Off-support control via PDW): The PDW construction (Appendix A.4) verifies off-support dual feasibility $|\tilde{z}_k| < 1$ for $k \notin S^*$ using the SSC gap $\Delta > 0$, which ensures no off-support atom is selected. This replaces the role of the cone RE in controlling the off-support error. The PDW approach decomposes the recovery guarantee into:

- **On-support accuracy:** controlled by support-block RE (Steps 1–3 above);
- **Off-support exclusion:** controlled by SSC and dual certificate (Lemma 47 and Lemma 49).

□

Remark 41 (Why generic cone RE fails in ultra-coherent dictionaries). *For completeness, we verify that the standard coherence-based cone RE argument fails in our setting, justifying the support-block approach above.*

For $v \in C(S^*, 3)$, the generic block decomposition of the quadratic form gives:

$$v^\top \Sigma v = v_{S^*}^\top \Sigma_{S^*} v_{S^*} + 2v_{S^*}^\top \Sigma_{S^*,(S^*)^c} v_{(S^*)^c} + v_{(S^*)^c}^\top \Sigma_{(S^*)^c} v_{(S^*)^c}.$$

Bounding the cross-term via coherence:

$$|v_{S^*}^\top \Sigma_{S^*,(S^*)^c} v_{(S^*)^c}| \leq \mu_{\max} \|v_{S^*}\|_1 \|v_{(S^*)^c}\|_1 \leq 3s \mu_{\max} \|v_{S^*}\|_2^2,$$

where we used the cone constraint and Cauchy–Schwarz. Since $\Sigma_{(S^*)^c} \geq 0$:

$$v^\top \Sigma v \geq \left(\frac{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2}{2} - 6s \mu_{\max} \right) \|v_{S^*}\|_2^2.$$

For positivity, this requires $\mu_{\max} \leq \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/(12s)$. In our setting ($s = 5$, $\kappa_{\text{pop}} = 0.026$, $\mu_{\max} \approx 0.997$), the cross-term contribution is $6s\mu_{\max} \approx 30$ while $\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/2 \approx 3.4 \times 10^{-4}$, a gap of five orders of magnitude. This quantitative failure is typical of ultra-coherent dictionaries and explains why the support-block RE approach is essential: it avoids controlling the full off-support interaction by delegating off-support exclusion to the SSC-based dual certificate.

A.3. Appendix C: Concentration Bounds

A.3.1. Scalar Bernstein Inequality

Theorem 42 (Bernstein; see Boucheron–Lugosi–Massart 2013, Theorem 2.10). *Let Y_1, \dots, Y_N be independent with $\mathbb{E}[Y_i] = 0$, $|Y_i| \leq B$, and $\frac{1}{N} \sum \text{Var}(Y_i) \leq v$. Then for all $t > 0$,*

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\frac{1}{N} \left| \sum_{i=1}^N Y_i \right| \geq t\right) \leq 2 \exp\left(-\frac{Nt^2/2}{v + Bt/3}\right). \quad (50)$$

A.3.2. Concentration of the Support Block $\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*}$

We concentrate the $s \times s$ support-block $\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*}$ rather than the full $D \times D$ Gram matrix. For each entry $(j, k) \in S^* \times S^*$, let $Y_i^{(j,k)} = \psi_j(x_i)\psi_k(x_i) - \Sigma_{jk}$.

By boundedness $|\psi_j(x)| \leq L$:

- $|Y_i^{(j,k)}| \leq 2L^2 =: B$.
- $\text{Var}(Y_i^{(j,k)}) = \mathbb{E}[(\psi_j\psi_k)^2] - \Sigma_{jk}^2 \leq \mathbb{E}[\psi_j^2\psi_k^2] \leq L^2\mathbb{E}[\psi_j^2] = L^2 =: v$. (Here we used $|\psi_k| \leq L$ and $\mathbb{E}[\psi_j^2] = 1$.)

Note on tightness: This variance bound is conservative; for orthogonal polynomial atoms, $\mathbb{E}[\psi_j^2\psi_k^2]$ has special structure (it equals a linear combination of Clebsch–Gordan coefficients for Jacobi polynomials). Exploiting this structure, or using matrix Bernstein inequalities with effective rank, could improve the constant by a factor of $O(s)$; see Tropp [31] for the relevant tools.

Applying Theorem 42 to each entry and taking a union bound over the s^2 entries of $\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*} - \Sigma_{S^*}$:

$$\mathbb{P}(\|\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*} - \Sigma_{S^*}\|_{\max} \geq t) \leq 2s^2 \exp\left(-\frac{Nt^2/2}{L^2 + 2L^2t/3}\right) \leq 2s^2 \exp\left(-\frac{Nt^2}{4L^2}\right), \quad (51)$$

where the last step uses $t \leq 1$ (which holds in our regime) so that $L^2 + 2L^2t/3 \leq 2L^2$.

A.3.3. From Max-Norm to Operator Norm

Since $\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*} - \Sigma_{S^*}$ is $s \times s$,

$$\|\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*} - \Sigma_{S^*}\|_{\text{op}} \leq s \cdot \|\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*} - \Sigma_{S^*}\|_{\text{max}}. \quad (52)$$

By Weyl's inequality, $|\lambda_{\min}(\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*}) - \lambda_{\min}(\Sigma_{S^*})| \leq \|\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*} - \Sigma_{S^*}\|_{\text{op}}$.

A.3.4. Solving for N

Set $s \cdot t = \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/4$ (so that the operator-norm perturbation is at most $\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/4$, half of the population eigenvalue gap).

Then $t = \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/(4s)$.

Require the failure probability $\leq \delta$:

$$2s^2 \exp\left(-\frac{N\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4}{64s^2L^2}\right) \leq \delta \iff N \geq \frac{64L^2s^2 \log(2s^2/\delta)}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4}. \quad (53)$$

With explicit constants: $C_{\text{conc}} = 64L^2$ from the derivation above. (A cruder variance bound $v = L^4$ would give $C_{\text{conc}} = 128L^4$; we state the tighter bound here.)

A.3.5. Matrix Bernstein Route and Partial Rigorous Bounds

The entry-wise bound incurs a union bound over s^2 entries. A standard alternative is to apply matrix concentration directly to $\|\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*} - \Sigma_{S^*}\|_{\text{op}}$. In this appendix we record the setup and where the unresolved difficulty enters.

Theorem 43 (Matrix Bernstein for averages, adapted from [31]). *Let $\mathbf{X}_1, \dots, \mathbf{X}_N \in \mathbb{R}^{s \times s}$ be independent symmetric matrices with $\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{X}_i] = 0$, $\|\mathbf{X}_i\|_{\text{op}} \leq R$ almost surely, and*

$$v := \left\| \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{X}_1^2] \right\|_{\text{op}}.$$

Then for any $t > 0$,

$$\mathbb{P}\left(\left\| \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{X}_i \right\|_{\text{op}} \geq t\right) \leq 2s \exp\left(-\frac{Nt^2}{2(v + Rt/3)}\right).$$

Application to Gram matrix estimation. Let $u_i := \psi_{S^*}(x_i) \in \mathbb{R}^s$, $\Sigma_{S^*} := \mathbb{E}[u_i u_i^\top]$, and

$$X_i := u_i u_i^\top - \Sigma_{S^*}.$$

Then

$$\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*} - \Sigma_{S^*} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N X_i.$$

Define the fourth moment operator

$$\mathbf{M} := \mathbb{E}[\|u_i\|_2^2 u_i u_i^\top].$$

A direct expansion gives

$$X_i^2 = \|u_i\|_2^2 u_i u_i^\top - u_i u_i^\top \Sigma_{S^*} - \Sigma_{S^*} u_i u_i^\top + \Sigma_{S^*}^2,$$

hence

$$\mathbb{E}[X_i^2] = \mathbf{M} - \Sigma_{S^*}^2, \quad v = \left\| \mathbf{M} - \Sigma_{S^*}^2 \right\|_{\text{op}}.$$

Proposition 44 (Fixed- K matrix Bernstein bound with full proof). *Suppose*

$$\|\mathbf{M} - \Sigma_{S^*}^2\|_{\text{op}} \leq C_K s \quad \text{and} \quad \|u_i\|_2^2 \leq sL^2 \text{ a.s.}$$

for constants C_K, L independent of (N, D) . Then for $t = \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/4$, with probability at least $1 - \delta$,

$$\|\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*} - \Sigma_{S^*}\|_{\text{op}} \leq t$$

whenever

$$N \geq C \log \frac{2s}{\delta} \left(\frac{C_K s}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4} + \frac{sL^2}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2} \right),$$

for a universal constant $C > 0$. In particular, for bounded L and $\kappa_{\text{pop}} \leq 1$, the rate is of order

$$N \gtrsim \frac{s \log(s/\delta)}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4}.$$

Proof. Apply the matrix Bernstein theorem to $X_i = u_i u_i^\top - \Sigma_{S^*}$. First, using $\|u_i u_i^\top\|_{\text{op}} = \|u_i\|_2^2$,

$$\|X_i\|_{\text{op}} \leq \|u_i\|_2^2 + \|\Sigma_{S^*}\|_{\text{op}} \leq sL^2 + \|\Sigma_{S^*}\|_{\text{op}}.$$

By the block form in Theorem 8, $\|\Sigma_{S^*}\|_{\text{op}} \leq 2$, so $R \leq sL^2 + 2$. Second, by assumption,

$$v = \|\mathbb{E}[X_i^2]\|_{\text{op}} = \|\mathbf{M} - \Sigma_{S^*}^2\|_{\text{op}} \leq C_K s.$$

Therefore, for any $t > 0$,

$$\mathbb{P}(\|\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*} - \Sigma_{S^*}\|_{\text{op}} \geq t) \leq 2s \exp\left(-\frac{Nt^2}{2(C_K s + (sL^2 + 2)t/3)}\right).$$

Set $t = \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/4$ and require the right side to be at most δ . This is implied by

$$N \geq 2 \log \frac{2s}{\delta} \left(\frac{C_K s}{t^2} + \frac{sL^2 + 2}{3t} \right),$$

which gives

$$N \geq C \log \frac{2s}{\delta} \left(\frac{C_K s}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4} + \frac{sL^2}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2} \right)$$

after absorbing universal constants and the additive $2/\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2$ term. Finally, if $\|\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*} - \Sigma_{S^*}\|_{\text{op}} \leq \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/4$, then Weyl's inequality and Theorem 8 imply

$$\lambda_{\min}(\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*}) \geq \lambda_{\min}(\Sigma_{S^*}) - \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/4 \geq \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/2 - \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/4 = \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/4.$$

□

Trace and fourth moment control in fixed K . For fixed K , the smooth block has at most $K + 1$ atoms, hence $s \leq K + 2$ in the current model. If each selected atom has finite $L^4(\mu)$ moment bounded by a constant depending on (K, α, β, b) , then

$$\text{tr}(\mathbf{B}) = \sum_{j=1}^s \mathbb{E}[u_j^4] \leq C_K s, \quad \mathbf{B}_{jk} := \mathbb{E}[u_j^2 u_k^2].$$

Since

$$\mathbb{E}\|u\|_2^4 = \sum_{j,k=1}^s \mathbb{E}[u_j^2 u_k^2] = \mathbf{1}^\top \mathbf{B} \mathbf{1} \leq s \|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}} \leq s \text{tr}(\mathbf{B}),$$

we get $\mathbb{E}\|u\|_2^4 \leq C_K s^2$, and because $s \leq K+2$, this is bounded by a constant multiple of s . Therefore $v = \|\mathbf{M} - \Sigma_{S^*}^2\|_{\text{op}} \leq C_K s$ in fixed K regimes, which verifies the hypothesis used in Proposition 44.

Bounding $\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}}$:

1. **Fixed K (trace bound):** For fixed polynomial degree K independent of s :

$$\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}} \leq \text{tr}(\mathbf{B}) = \sum_{j=1}^s \mathbb{E}[\phi_j^4] \leq s \cdot C(K),$$

where $C(K) = O(L^4)$ depends only on K . This yields $\sigma^2 = O(Ns)$.

2. **Deterministic Gershgorin bound:**

$$\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}} \leq \max_j \sum_{k=1}^s |\mathbf{B}_{jk}| \leq sL^4,$$

because $|\mathbf{B}_{jk}| \leq \int_0^1 L^4 w(x) dx = L^4$. This is crude but completely explicit.

3. $K \sim s$ (**rigorous coarse bound**): Under standard Jacobi endpoint and interior kernel estimates, Proposition 45 gives

$$\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}} \leq C_{\beta,b} s^{3/2}.$$

4. $K \sim s$ (**empirical observation**): For Jacobi polynomials with $K \sim s$, numerical computation (Appendix A.3.6) suggests:

$$\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}} \sim s^{1.809},$$

yielding $\sigma^2 = O(Ns^{1.809})$.

Proposition 45 (Coarse $K \sim s$ fourth moment bound by interval splitting). *Let $w(x) = x^\beta(1-x)^b$ with $\beta, b > -1$, and let $\{\phi_k\}_{k=0}^s$ be shifted Jacobi polynomials orthonormal in $L^2(w)$. Define*

$$\mathbf{B}_{jk} = \int_0^1 \phi_j(x)^2 \phi_k(x)^2 w(x) dx.$$

Assume the following standard Jacobi estimates for constants depending only on (β, b) :

1. Endpoint kernel bound on $[0, s^{-2}]$: $K_s(x, x) \leq C_1 s^{2\beta+2}$.
2. Interior kernel bound on $[s^{-2}, 1]$: $K_s(x, x) \leq C_2 s x^{-1/2}$.
3. Uniform L^4 envelope for $j \leq s$: $\|\phi_j\|_{L^4(w)}^2 \leq C_3 s^{1/2}$.

Then

$$\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}} \leq C_{\beta,b} s^{3/2}.$$

Proof. By Gershgorin,

$$\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}} \leq \max_j \sum_{k=0}^s \mathbf{B}_{jk} = \max_j \int_0^1 \phi_j(x)^2 K_s(x, x) w(x) dx.$$

Fix $j \leq s$ and split at $x_\star = s^{-2}$:

$$R_j := \int_0^1 \phi_j^2 K_s w = \int_0^{x_\star} \phi_j^2 K_s w + \int_{x_\star}^1 \phi_j^2 K_s w =: R_j^{\text{end}} + R_j^{\text{int}}.$$

For R_j^{end} , use assumption 1 and the local $L^2(w)$ mass estimate implied by Mehler Heine asymptotics to get $R_j^{\text{end}} \leq Cs^{1/2}$. For R_j^{int} , apply Cauchy Schwarz:

$$R_j^{\text{int}} \leq \|K_s\|_{L^2(w, [x_\star, 1])} \|\phi_j^2\|_{L^2(w)} = \|K_s\|_{L^2(w, [x_\star, 1])} \|\phi_j\|_{L^4(w)}^2.$$

Assumption 2 gives $\|K_s\|_{L^2(w, [x_\star, 1])} \leq Cs$, and assumption 3 gives $\|\phi_j\|_{L^4(w)}^2 \leq Cs^{1/2}$, hence $R_j^{\text{int}} \leq Cs^{3/2}$. Therefore $R_j \leq Cs^{3/2}$ uniformly in j , which yields $\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}} \leq Cs^{3/2}$. \square

Formal consequence if the variance proxy is controlled: Setting $t = \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/4$ and solving for N :

$$N \gtrsim \frac{(\sigma^2/N + Rt/3) \log(s/\delta)}{t^2} \approx \frac{\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}} \log(s/\delta)}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4}.$$

This would give:

- Fixed K : $N \gtrsim \frac{s \log s}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4}$.
- $K \sim s$ (rigorous coarse): $N \gtrsim \frac{s^{1.5} \log s}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4}$.
- $K \sim s$ (empirical): $N \gtrsim \frac{s^{1.809} \log s}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4}$.

The fixed K and $K \sim s$ coarse bounds are rigorous under the assumptions stated above. The exponent 1.809 is numerical evidence.

A.3.6. Christoffel Function Computation and Numerical Evidence

We numerically verify the fourth-moment scaling $\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}}$ for Jacobi polynomial dictionaries ($\beta = 0.55$, $b = 0$). In the normalized $K = s$ protocol, numerical evidence gives $\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}} \sim s^{1.809}$ (Figure 5); detailed numerical tables are collected in Section B.

Remark 46 (Theory-experiment gap). *With $s = 5$, $\kappa_{\text{pop}} \approx 0.021$, and $L \approx 1$, the entry-wise sufficient condition gives $N = O(10^{10})$; the fourth-moment matrix route remains of high polynomial order in s in the normalized $K = s$ regime; the small-ball route gives a conditional linear-in- s concentration term; experiments achieve perfect recovery at $N \leq 420$. This gap (factor $\sim 10^7$ – 10^8) reflects worst-case conservatism in Bernstein bounds and special algebraic structure of Jacobi polynomial recurrences. **The theoretical bounds are sufficient conditions, not necessary ones;** see Section B for additional technical discussion.*

A.3.7. Proof of Lemma 9

Combining the above steps, with probability $1 - \delta$,

$$v^\top \hat{\Sigma} v = v^\top \Sigma v + v^\top (\hat{\Sigma} - \Sigma) v \geq \gamma \|v\|_2^2 - \frac{\gamma}{2} \|v\|_2^2 = \frac{\gamma}{2} \|v\|_2^2, \quad (54)$$

provided N satisfies the stated bound.

A.4. Appendix D: Primal-Dual Witness

A.4.1. KKT Conditions

LASSO solution \hat{c} satisfies:

$$\frac{1}{N} \Phi^\top (y - \Phi \hat{c}) = \lambda_N \hat{z}, \quad \hat{z} \in \partial \|\hat{c}\|_1. \quad (55)$$

Figure 3: Log-log plot of $\|B\|_{op}$ versus n for Jacobi polynomial dictionaries ($\beta = 0.55$). Data points with power-law fit give slope 1.809 in the normalized $K = s$ protocol. The rigorous coarse benchmark is exponent 1.5 from Proposition 45.

A.4.2. Restricted Problem

Define $\tilde{c}_{S^*} = \arg \min_{c \in \mathbb{R}^{|S^*|}} \frac{1}{2N} \|y - \Phi_{S^*} c\|_2^2 + \lambda_N \|c\|_1$, and set $\tilde{c}_{(S^*)^c} = 0$. By Lemma 9, $\lambda_{\min}(\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*}) \geq \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/4$, so the restricted LASSO estimation error satisfies (see Bühlmann–van de Geer 2011, Theorem 6.1, or Wainwright 2019, Theorem 7.19):

$$\|\tilde{c}_{S^*} - c_{S^*}^*\|_2 \leq \frac{4\sqrt{s} \lambda_N}{\lambda_{\min}(\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*})} \leq \frac{16\sqrt{s} \lambda_N}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2}. \quad (56)$$

A.4.3. Dual Certificate

Define:

$$\tilde{z}_{S^*} = \text{sign}(c_{S^*}^*) + \frac{1}{\lambda_N N} \Phi_{S^*}^\top \xi, \quad (57)$$

$$\tilde{z}_{(S^*)^c} = \frac{1}{\lambda_N N} \Phi_{(S^*)^c}^\top (y - \Phi_{S^*} \tilde{c}_{S^*}), \quad (58)$$

where $\xi = y - \Phi c^*$ is the noise vector with $\xi_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$.

A.4.4. Sign Consistency for Singular Atom

Lemma 47 (Sign consistency via SSC). *Under SSC with gap $\Delta > 0$ and $\lambda_N = 4\sigma\sqrt{(\log D + \log(1/\delta))/N}$, if $N \geq C \frac{\sigma^2 \log D}{\Delta^2}$, then with probability $1 - \delta/2$,*

$$|\tilde{z}_1| = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{sign}(\tilde{z}_1) = \text{sign}(c_1^*). \quad (59)$$

Proof. Decompose:

$$\tilde{z}_1 = \text{sign}(c_1^*) + \frac{1}{\lambda_N N} \sum_{i=1}^N \psi_1(x_i) \xi_i + \frac{1}{\lambda_N N} \sum_{i=1}^N \psi_1(x_i) (u(x_i) - \Phi_{S^*}(x_i)^\top \tilde{c}_{S^*}). \quad (60)$$

Noise term: By Gaussian concentration,

$$\left| \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \psi_1(x_i) \xi_i \right| = O_P \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} \right). \quad (61)$$

With $\lambda_N = \frac{4\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} \sqrt{\log D}$,

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_N} \cdot O_P \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}} \right) = O_P \left(\frac{1}{4\sqrt{\log D}} \right) \ll 1. \quad (62)$$

Signal term (SSC): By SSC,

$$|\mathbb{E}[\psi_1(x)u(x)]| \geq \max_{k \geq 2} |\mathbb{E}[\psi_k(x)u(x)]| + \Delta. \quad (63)$$

Empirical concentration gives

$$\left| \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \psi_1(x_i)u(x_i) - \mathbb{E}[\psi_1(x)u(x)] \right| = O_P \left(\sqrt{\frac{\log D}{N}} \right). \quad (64)$$

For $N \geq C \frac{\sigma^2 \log D}{\Delta^2}$, the empirical correlation

$$\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \psi_1(x_i)u(x_i) \geq \Delta/2 \quad (65)$$

with high probability. Thus

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_N N} \sum_{i=1}^N \psi_1(x_i)u(x_i) \geq \frac{\Delta}{2\lambda_N} = \frac{\Delta \sqrt{N}}{8\sigma \sqrt{\log D}} \gg 1. \quad (66)$$

Residual term: By the restricted estimator bound, $\|\tilde{c}_{S^*} - c_{S^*}^*\|_2 \leq 16\sqrt{s} \lambda_N / \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2$. Write $r_i := u(x_i) - \Phi_{S^*}(x_i)^\top \tilde{c}_{S^*} = \Phi_{S^*}(x_i)^\top (c_{S^*}^* - \tilde{c}_{S^*}) + \xi_i$. For the signal part, by Cauchy–Schwarz and $|\psi_1(x)| \leq L$:

$$\left| \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \psi_1(x_i) \Phi_{S^*}(x_i)^\top (c_{S^*}^* - \tilde{c}_{S^*}) \right| \leq L\sqrt{s} \|c_{S^*}^* - \tilde{c}_{S^*}\|_2 \leq \frac{16Ls \lambda_N}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2}. \quad (67)$$

(Here we used $\frac{1}{N} \sum_i |\psi_1(x_i)| \cdot \|\Phi_{S^*}(x_i)\|_2 \leq L\sqrt{s}$ by boundedness and the triangle inequality.) Dividing by λ_N , the residual contributes at most

$$\frac{16Ls}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2}. \quad (68)$$

Quantitative assessment of the residual. With the Nikolskiĭ bound $L = O(\sqrt{K})$ (Assumption 3), $s = 5$, $K = 10$, and $\kappa_{\text{pop}} = 0.026$:

$$\frac{16Ls}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2} \approx \frac{16 \cdot \sqrt{10} \cdot 5}{0.026^2} \approx 3.7 \times 10^5.$$

This factor is large, which explains why the *sufficient* sample complexity is conservative: the PDW construction demands that the estimation error be negligible relative to the SSC gap Δ , creating the sample size bottleneck $N \gg \sigma^2 s \log D / (\Delta^2 \kappa_{\text{pop}}^4)$. In practice, the factor is much smaller because:

- The empirical $\|\Phi_{S^*}(x_i)^\top (c^* - \tilde{c})\|$ concentrates well below the worst-case bound;
- The pointwise $\kappa(\alpha^*)$ replaces the uniform κ_{pop} , reducing the denominator by a factor of $(\kappa_{\text{point}}/\kappa_{\text{pop}})^2 \approx 33$;
- The boundedness constant for the singular atom is $\|\psi_1\|_\infty \leq ((2\alpha + \beta + 1)/(c_0 \delta^{2\alpha + \beta + 1}))^{1/2}$, which depends on $(c_0, \delta, \alpha, \beta)$ and not on K .

For this to be negligible relative to $\Delta/(2\lambda_N)$, we require $32Ls \lambda_N / \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2 \ll \Delta/\lambda_N$, i.e. $\lambda_N^2 \ll \Delta \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2 / (32Ls)$. Since $\lambda_N \sim \sigma \sqrt{\log D/N}$, this is satisfied when $N \gg \sigma^2 s \log D / (\Delta^2 \kappa_{\text{pop}}^4)$.

Combining, $\tilde{z}_1 = \text{sign}(c_1^*) + (\text{perturbation bounded by } 1/4)$, so $|\tilde{z}_1| = 1$ with correct sign. \square

A.4.5. Strict Dual Feasibility Off-Support

Lemma 48 (Cross-block bound). *Under RE and cone constraint, with high probability,*

$$\left\| \frac{1}{N} \Phi_{(S^*)^c}^\top \Phi_{S^*} \right\|_{\infty,2} \leq \frac{C}{\sqrt{s}}, \quad (69)$$

for some C depending on $L, \kappa_{\text{pop}}, \lambda_{\text{min}}^{\text{smooth}}$.

Proof. Population bound. For each $k \notin S^*$, the row $\Sigma_{k,S^*} = (\langle \psi_k, \psi_j \rangle)_{j \in S^*}$ satisfies $\|\Sigma_{k,S^*}\|_2 \leq \sqrt{s} \max_{j \in S^*} |\Sigma_{kj}| \leq \sqrt{s}$. More precisely, for $j = 1$ (singular atom): $|\Sigma_{k1}| \leq \cos \theta_{\alpha_k, K} = \sqrt{1 - \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2(\alpha_k)}$ (by the Friedrichs angle bound). For $j \in S_{\text{smooth}}$ (smooth atoms, orthonormal): by Bessel, $\sum_{j \in S_{\text{smooth}}} \Sigma_{kj}^2 \leq 1 - \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2(\alpha_k)$ if k is also a power-law atom, or $\Sigma_{kj} = 0$ if k is another smooth atom (by orthonormality).

Empirical bound. For each fixed pair (k, j) , the empirical correlation $\hat{\Sigma}_{kj} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i \psi_k(x_i) \psi_j(x_i)$ concentrates around Σ_{kj} by Bernstein's inequality: $|\hat{\Sigma}_{kj} - \Sigma_{kj}| \leq t$ with probability $\geq 1 - 2e^{-Nt^2/(4L^2)}$. Union-bounding over $(D-s) \times s$ pairs and setting $t = O(\sqrt{\log(Ds/\delta)/N})$ transfers the population bound to the empirical bound. \square

Lemma 49 (Off-support dual feasibility). *Under the conditions of Theorem 18, for all $k \notin S^*$,*

$$|\tilde{z}_k| \leq 1 - \eta, \quad \eta = \frac{\Delta}{2\lambda_N} > 0. \quad (70)$$

Proof. Decompose:

$$\tilde{z}_k = \frac{1}{\lambda_N N} \sum_{i=1}^N \psi_k(x_i) \xi_i + \frac{1}{\lambda_N N} \sum_{i=1}^N \psi_k(x_i) (u(x_i) - \Phi_{S^*}(x_i)^\top \tilde{c}_{S^*}). \quad (71)$$

Noise: By Gaussian tail (union bound over $(S^*)^c$),

$$\mathbb{P} \left(\max_{k \notin S^*} \left| \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \psi_k(x_i) \xi_i \right| > \frac{\lambda_N}{4} \right) \leq \delta/2. \quad (72)$$

Model misfit: Using Lemma 48 and the restricted estimator bound $\|\tilde{c}_{S^*} - c_{S^*}^*\|_2 \leq 16\sqrt{s} \lambda_N / \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2$:

$$\left| \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \psi_k(x_i) (u(x_i) - \Phi_{S^*}(x_i)^\top \tilde{c}_{S^*}) \right| \leq \left\| \frac{1}{N} \Phi_{(S^*)^c}^\top \Phi_{S^*} \right\|_{\infty,2} \|\tilde{c}_{S^*} - c_{S^*}^*\|_2 \quad (73)$$

$$\leq \frac{C}{\sqrt{s}} \cdot \frac{16\sqrt{s} \lambda_N}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2} = \frac{16C \lambda_N}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^2}. \quad (74)$$

This is at most $\lambda_N/4$ when $C \leq \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/64$, which holds for sufficiently large N (so that the empirical cross-block concentrates near the population value, which is $O(\sqrt{1 - \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2})$).

By SSC, the population correlation $|\langle \psi_k, u \rangle_\mu| \leq |\langle \psi_1, u \rangle_\mu| - \Delta$, and empirical concentration (Bernstein with union bound over $D-s$ atoms) ensures the empirical gap is at least $\Delta/2$ when $N \geq C_2 \sigma^2 \log D/\Delta^2$.

Combining the three contributions:

- Noise: $\frac{1}{\lambda_N N} \left| \sum_i \psi_k(x_i) \xi_i \right| \leq 1/4$;
- Model misfit: $\frac{1}{\lambda_N N} \left| \sum_i \psi_k(x_i) \Phi_{S^*}(x_i)^\top (\tilde{c} - c^*) \right| \leq 1/4$;
- Signal (by SSC): the empirical correlation satisfies $\left| \frac{1}{N} \sum_i \psi_k(x_i) u(x_i) \right| \leq \left| \frac{1}{N} \sum_i \psi_1(x_i) u(x_i) \right| - \Delta/2$.

The dual variable satisfies $|\tilde{z}_k| \leq \frac{1}{\lambda_N} (\frac{\lambda_N}{4} + \frac{\lambda_N}{4} + |\langle \psi_k, u \rangle_\mu|)$. Since the SSC constrains the signal contribution, the key bound is:

$$|\tilde{z}_k| \leq \underbrace{\frac{1}{4}}_{\text{noise}} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{4}}_{\text{misfit}} + \underbrace{\frac{|\langle \psi_k, u \rangle_\mu|}{\lambda_N}}_{\text{signal}} \leq \frac{1}{2} + \frac{|\langle \psi_1, u \rangle_\mu| - \Delta/2}{\lambda_N}. \quad (75)$$

For this to be strictly less than 1, it suffices that $|\langle \psi_1, u \rangle_\mu|/\lambda_N \leq 1 - \Delta/(4\lambda_N)$, which gives $|\tilde{z}_k| \leq 1 - \Delta/(4\lambda_N)$, establishing strict dual feasibility with slack $\eta = \Delta/(4\lambda_N) > 0$. \square

A.4.6. Proof of Theorem 18

Proof. By Lemmas 47 and 49, the primal-dual pair (\tilde{c}, \tilde{z}) satisfies:

1. \tilde{c}_{S^*} is the restricted LASSO solution with $\|\tilde{c}_{S^*} - c_{S^*}^*\|_2 \leq 16\sqrt{s} \lambda_N / \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2$; $\tilde{c}_{(S^*)^c} = 0$.
2. $|\tilde{z}_1| = 1$ with $\text{sign}(\tilde{z}_1) = \text{sign}(c_1^*)$.
3. $|\tilde{z}_k| < 1$ for all $k \notin S^*$.

By the primal-dual witness theorem (Wainwright 2009, Theorem 1; see also Bühlmann–van de Geer 2011, Theorem 7.21, or Wainwright 2019, Theorem 7.21), conditions (1)–(3) ensure that \tilde{c} is the unique LASSO solution, and $\text{supp}(\tilde{c}) = S^*$. In particular, $1 \in \text{supp}(\tilde{c})$.

The ℓ_2 error bound in Theorem 18(2) follows from the restricted eigenvalue $\lambda_{\min}(\hat{\Sigma}_{S^*}) \geq \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/4$ and the standard oracle inequality for the restricted LASSO. \square

A.5. Appendix E: Dictionary Grid Analysis

A.5.1. Robustness and SSC

In this section, we provide rigorous bounds for the correlation decay, the statistical Source Separation Condition (SSC), and the recovery robustness under grid discretization. We assume the weight function is of the Jacobi type $w(x) = x^\beta(1-x)^b$ with $\beta, b > -1$.

Uniform Quadratic Decay of Correlation.

Proposition 50 (Uniform Local Decay). *Let $\psi_\alpha(x) = c_\alpha x^\alpha$ be the normalized atom. Consider a compact parameter interval $\mathcal{A} = [\alpha_{\min}, \alpha_{\max}] \subset (-1/2, \infty)$. There exists a uniform curvature constant $\epsilon_{\min} > 0$ such that for any $\alpha \in \mathcal{A}$ and sufficiently small shift δ , the correlation satisfies:*

$$|\langle \psi_\alpha, \psi_{\alpha+\delta} \rangle_w| \leq 1 - \epsilon_{\min} \delta^2 + C_3 |\delta|^3. \quad (76)$$

Specifically, $\epsilon_{\min} = \frac{1}{2} \inf_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \mathcal{I}(\alpha)$, where $\mathcal{I}(\alpha) = \psi^{(1)}(2\alpha+1) - \psi^{(1)}(2\alpha+\beta+b+2)$ is the Fisher Information metric. The remainder is bounded by $C_3 \leq \frac{1}{6} \sup_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} |\psi^{(2)}(2\alpha+1) - \psi^{(2)}(2\alpha+\beta+b+2)|$.

Proof. Step 1 (Smoothness of the correlation). Write $c_\alpha = \|x^\alpha\|_w^{-1}$ and

$$\langle \psi_\alpha, \psi_{\alpha+\delta} \rangle_w = \frac{\int_0^1 x^{2\alpha+\delta} w(x) dx}{\|x^\alpha\|_w \|x^{\alpha+\delta}\|_w}.$$

The numerator $I(\alpha, \delta) := \int_0^1 x^{2\alpha+\delta} w(x) dx$ is C^∞ in both α and δ by dominated convergence: for any $k \geq 1$, $\partial_\delta^k I = \int_0^1 x^{2\alpha+\delta} (\ln x)^k w(x) dx$, and $|x^{2\alpha+\delta} (\ln x)^k w(x)| \leq C_k w(x) \in L^1$ for $\alpha \geq \alpha_{\min} > -1/2$ and $|\delta| \leq 1$ (since $|x^a (\ln x)^k|$ is bounded on $(0, 1]$ for $a > -1/2$). The denominator involves $\|x^\alpha\|_w = \sqrt{I(\alpha, 0)}$ and $\|x^{\alpha+\delta}\|_w = \sqrt{I(\alpha+\delta, 0)}$, both smooth and strictly positive on \mathcal{A} . Hence $\langle \psi_\alpha, \psi_{\alpha+\delta} \rangle_w$ is C^∞ in δ on a neighborhood of 0.

Step 2 (Taylor expansion). The log-correlation $L(\delta) = \ln \langle \psi_\alpha, \psi_{\alpha+\delta} \rangle_w$ satisfies $L(0) = 0$ (since $\|\psi_\alpha\| = 1$) and $L'(0) = 0$ (the correlation is maximized at $\delta = 0$, giving a critical point). Taylor's theorem with Lagrange remainder yields $L(\delta) = \frac{1}{2} L''(0) \delta^2 + \frac{1}{6} L'''(\xi) \delta^3$ for some ξ between 0 and δ .

A direct computation gives $L''(0) = -\mathcal{I}(\alpha)$ where $\mathcal{I}(\alpha) = \psi^{(1)}(2\alpha+1) - \psi^{(1)}(2\alpha+\beta+b+2)$ and $\psi^{(1)}$ is the trigamma function.

Step 3 (Uniform positivity). Since $\psi^{(1)}(z)$ is strictly decreasing for $z > 0$ and the argument gap is $\beta + b + 1 > 0$ (as $\beta, b > -1$), we have $\mathcal{I}(\alpha) > 0$ for every $\alpha \in \mathcal{A}$. Continuity of \mathcal{I} on the compact set \mathcal{A} gives $c_{\min} = \frac{1}{2} \inf_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \mathcal{I}(\alpha) > 0$. The remainder bound $C_3 \leq \frac{1}{6} \sup_{\alpha} |L'''|$ follows from the uniform bound on $\psi^{(2)}$ (tetragamma function) on \mathcal{A} .

Exponentiating: $\langle \psi_{\alpha}, \psi_{\alpha+\delta} \rangle_w = e^{L(\delta)} \leq e^{-c_{\min}\delta^2 + C_3|\delta|^3} \leq 1 - c_{\min}\delta^2 + C_3|\delta|^3$, using $e^{-x} \leq 1 - x + x^2/2$ and absorbing higher-order terms into the $C_3|\delta|^3$ remainder. \square

Remark 51 (Numerical values of c_{\min}). *For the experimental parameters $\beta = 0.55$, $b = 0$, and grid $\mathcal{A} = [0.1, 0.9]$:*

- The Fisher information is $\mathcal{I}(\alpha) = \psi^{(1)}(2\alpha + 1) - \psi^{(1)}(2\alpha + 2.55)$, where $\psi^{(1)}$ is the trigamma function.
- At $\alpha = 0.1$: $\mathcal{I}(0.1) = \psi^{(1)}(1.2) - \psi^{(1)}(2.75) \approx 0.92 - 0.45 = 0.47$.
- At $\alpha = 0.9$: $\mathcal{I}(0.9) = \psi^{(1)}(2.8) - \psi^{(1)}(4.35) \approx 0.40 - 0.26 = 0.14$.
- Thus $c_{\min} = \frac{1}{2} \inf_{\alpha \in [0.1, 0.9]} \mathcal{I}(\alpha) \approx \frac{1}{2} \times 0.14 = 0.07$.

This value is distinct from $\kappa_{\text{pop}} \approx 0.026$, which is the Müntz–Szász separation bound. The constant c_{\min} controls the curvature of the correlation function between neighboring singular atoms (in α -space), while κ_{pop} controls the distance between singular atoms and the polynomial subspace (in function space). Both contribute to the sample complexity, but through different mechanisms: κ_{pop} via the restricted eigenvalue condition, and c_{\min} via the grid resolution for distinguishing nearby singular exponents.

SSC Gap with Smooth Contamination. In this subsection, we use Δ_{SSC} to denote the SSC gap (identical to Δ in Definition 15) to distinguish it from the grid spacing parameter $\Delta\alpha$.

Proposition 52 (SSC Gap with Smooth Components). *Let the true signal be $u = c_1^* \psi_{\alpha^*} + u_{\text{smooth}}$, where $u_{\text{smooth}} = \sum_{j=2}^s c_j^* \phi_j$. Assume the true parameter α^* is sufficiently close to a grid point α_{m_0} such that $\min_m |\alpha^* - \alpha_m| \leq \frac{\Delta\alpha}{4}$. Let $\underline{\kappa} := \inf_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \kappa(\alpha)$ be the uniform Müntz–Szász separation over the grid. The SSC gap $\Delta_{\text{SSC}} := |\langle \psi_{m_0}, u \rangle| - \max_{k \neq m_0} |\langle \psi_k, u \rangle|$ satisfies:*

$$\Delta_{\text{SSC}} \geq |c_1^*| \cdot c_{\min} \frac{(\Delta\alpha)^2}{2} - 2\|c_{\text{smooth}}\|_1 \sqrt{1 - \underline{\kappa}^2} - C_3 |c_1^*| |\Delta\alpha|^3. \quad (77)$$

Sufficient condition for $\Delta_{\text{SSC}} > 0$: *The SSC gap is strictly positive whenever the singular component dominates the smooth contamination in the following precise sense:*

$$|c_1^*| > \frac{4\|c_{\text{smooth}}\|_1 \sqrt{1 - \underline{\kappa}^2}}{c_{\min} (\Delta\alpha)^2 - 2C_3 |\Delta\alpha|^3}, \quad (78)$$

provided $\Delta\alpha$ is small enough that $c_{\min}(\Delta\alpha)^2 > 2C_3 |\Delta\alpha|^3$, i.e. $|\Delta\alpha| < c_{\min}/(2C_3)$.

Proof. Let $\epsilon = |\alpha^* - \alpha_{m_0}| \leq \Delta\alpha/4$. The distance to the second nearest grid point α_{m_1} is $\delta_{\text{sec}} \geq \Delta\alpha - \epsilon \geq \frac{3\Delta\alpha}{4}$. By Proposition 1, the correlation gap between the best and second-best atom is:

$$\text{Gap}_{\text{signal}} \approx |c_1^*| \left[(1 - c_{\min}\epsilon^2) - (1 - c_{\min}\delta_{\text{sec}}^2) \right] = |c_1^*| c_{\min} (\delta_{\text{sec}}^2 - \epsilon^2). \quad (79)$$

Minimizing this over $0 \leq \epsilon \leq \Delta\alpha/4$, the worst case occurs at the boundary $\epsilon = \Delta\alpha/4$, yielding:

$$\delta_{\text{sec}}^2 - \epsilon^2 \geq \left(\frac{3\Delta\alpha}{4}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{\Delta\alpha}{4}\right)^2 = \frac{8}{16}(\Delta\alpha)^2 = \frac{1}{2}(\Delta\alpha)^2. \quad (80)$$

For the smooth components, we bound the cross-correlation $|\langle \psi_k, \phi_j \rangle|$. Since $\phi_j \in P_K$ by Assumption 2, and $\psi_k = \psi_{\alpha_k}$ is a singular atom with Friedrichs angle θ_k to P_K , we have $|\langle \psi_k, \phi_j \rangle| \leq \cos \theta_k \leq \sqrt{1 - \kappa(\alpha_k)^2}$. Under the uniformity assumption that \mathcal{A} is compact, we have $\inf_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \kappa(\alpha) \geq \underline{\kappa} > 0$, so $|\langle \psi_k, \phi_j \rangle| \leq \sqrt{1 - \underline{\kappa}^2}$ uniformly over all grid atoms.

The smooth term reduces the gap by at most $2 \sum |c_j^*| |\langle \psi_k, \phi_j \rangle| \leq 2\|c_{\text{smooth}}\|_1 \sqrt{1 - \underline{\kappa}^2}$. Note that this bound is worst-case over all sign patterns of the smooth coefficients; favorable sign alignment could reduce this contamination term. Combining these bounds yields the result. \square

Robustness and Sample Complexity.

Proposition 53 (Lipschitz Robustness). *Assume the RE condition holds with constant γ . Let $\epsilon = \min_m |\alpha^* - \alpha_m|$. The bias induced by grid mismatch is bounded by:*

$$\|Bias\|_2 \leq \frac{2|c_1^*|L_{\max}\epsilon}{\gamma}, \quad \text{where } L_{\max} = \sup_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \sqrt{I(\alpha)}. \quad (81)$$

Proof. The tangent vector norm is $\|\partial_\alpha \psi_\alpha\|_w^2 = \frac{1}{4}I(\alpha)$. The rest follows from standard RE stability analysis (Theorem 8). \square

Corollary 54 (Connection to Theorems 18 and 21). *Substituting the gap from Proposition 52 into Theorem 18, exact support recovery requires:*

$$N \gtrsim \max \left\{ \frac{s^2 \log s}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4}, \frac{\sigma^2 \log D}{\Delta_{\text{SSC}}^2} \right\} \quad \text{where } \Delta_{\text{SSC}} \propto |c_1^*| c_{\min}(\Delta\alpha)^2. \quad (82)$$

In the SSC-limited regime ($\sigma > 0$, fixed geometry), the dominant scaling is $N \sim \sigma^2 \log D / (|c_1^|^2 c_{\min}^2(\Delta\alpha)^4)$, explaining the $O((\Delta\alpha)^{-4})$ behavior in the phase transition (Theorem 21).*

A.5.4 Numerical Validation and Connection to Experiments

To validate the theoretical bounds derived in Propositions 1–3, we performed numerical evaluations of the curvature and Lipschitz constants using the standard Python SciPy library.

Numerical Constants. For the representative parameter setting used in our experiments ($\beta = 0.55$, $b = 0$) over the parameter interval $\mathcal{A} = [0.1, 0.9]$, the evaluation yields:

$$c_{\min} \approx 0.07, \quad L_{\max} \approx 1.414. \quad (83)$$

Here $c_{\min} = \frac{1}{2} \inf_{\alpha \in [0.1, 0.9]} I(\alpha) \approx \frac{1}{2} \times 0.14 = 0.07$ (see Remark 51 for the trigamma computation). These values confirm that the uniform curvature is strictly positive ($c_{\min} > 0$) and the manifold gradient is well-bounded ($L_{\max} < \infty$), ensuring the problem is well-posed in this regime. Notably, $L_{\max} \approx \sqrt{2}$ aligns with the analytical norm $\|\ln x\|_{L^2}$ in the unweighted limit, serving as a consistency check.

Computation details. The constants were computed using `scipy.special.polygamma` (trigamma function) and numerical integration. For reproducibility, the script is `compute_constants.py`. The Fisher information was evaluated on a fine grid (10^4 points) over $\mathcal{A} = [0.1, 0.9]$:

$$I(\alpha) = \psi^{(1)}(2\alpha + 1) - \psi^{(1)}(2\alpha + 2.55),$$

where $\psi^{(1)}$ is the trigamma function. The minimum was found at $\alpha \approx 0.9$, giving $I_{\min} \approx 0.1386$ and thus $c_{\min} = 0.5 \times 0.1386 \approx 0.0693 \approx 0.07$. The Lipschitz constant L_{\max} was computed via numerical integration of $\|\partial_\alpha \psi_\alpha\|_{L^2(\mu)}^2 = \frac{1}{4}I(\alpha)$ over the same grid.

Theoretical Explanation of Experimental Phase Transitions. These constants provide a quantitative explanation for the recovery results observed in Section 3:

- 1. Failure of Coarse Grid ($\Delta\alpha = 0.1$):** According to Proposition 2, the Source Separation Condition gap scales as $\Delta_{\text{SSC}} \propto c_{\min}(\Delta\alpha)^2$. For a coarse grid, while the inter-atom separation is large, the *representation error* (Proposition 3) dominates. With $c_{\min} \approx 0.07$, the geometric advantage is moderate but insufficient against smooth contamination. The required Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) for exact support recovery scales as $\text{SNR} \propto (c_{\min}(\Delta\alpha)^2)^{-1}$. For $\Delta\alpha = 0.1$, the correlation drop is significant, and the smooth contamination term $2\|c_{\text{smooth}}\|_1 \mu_{\text{cross}}$ easily overwhelms the gap $c_{\min}(\Delta\alpha)^2/2$, leading to the observed recovery rate of $\approx 8\%$.

2. **Success of Near-Oracle Grid** ($\Delta\alpha = 0.02$): When the grid is refined to $\Delta\alpha = 0.02$, the bias term bounded in Proposition 3 reduces linearly with ϵ . Although the SSC gap for distinguishing neighbors decreases, the critical factor for *off-grid* robustness is the modeling bias $\|\text{Bias}\|_2 \leq 2|c_1^*|L_{\max}\epsilon/\gamma$. With $L_{\max} \approx 1.41$ and $\epsilon \approx 0.01$, the bias is controlled below the noise floor, allowing the LASSO estimator to correctly identify the nearest grid point (Recovery = 1.00).

Remark 55 (Well-posed Regime). *Based on these numerical findings, we formally assume in our analysis that the weight parameters β, b and the domain \mathcal{A} are chosen such that $c_{\min} \geq c_0 > 0$ and $L_{\max} \leq L_0 < \infty$. This excludes pathological cases (e.g., $\beta \rightarrow -1^+$) where the Fisher information may degenerate.*

Remark 56 (Sample Complexity Exponent and Experimental Parameters). *The minimax sample complexity (Theorem 63) scales as $N \gtrsim s^{4(\alpha+\beta/2+1/2)} \log D$. For the experiments in Section 3 with parameters $\alpha = 0.35$ and $\beta = 0.55$ (mass exponent), the regime exponent is:*

$$\alpha + \frac{\beta}{2} + \frac{1}{2} = 0.35 + 0.275 + 0.5 = 1.125,$$

yielding $N \gtrsim s^{4.5} \log D$, which is slightly worse than the canonical s^4 scaling. The canonical s^4 scaling corresponds to the regime condition $\alpha + \beta/2 + 1/2 = 1$, satisfied by, e.g., $(\alpha, \beta) = (0.5, 0)$ (Lebesgue measure with square-root singularity). Our conservative theoretical bounds accommodate the full parameter range; the experimental success at $s \leq 5$ is consistent with both scalings.

A.6. Appendix F: Irrepresentability Conditions

We derive the relationship between SSC and the classical irrepresentable condition.

Proposition 57 (SSC implies structured irrepresentability). *Under the SSC (Definition 15) with gap $\Delta > 0$, and with $\lambda_{\min}(\Sigma_{S^*}) \geq \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/2$ (Theorem 8), the irrepresentable condition*

$$\left\| \Sigma_{(S^*)^c, S^*} \Sigma_{S^*, S^*}^{-1} \text{sign}(c_{S^*}^*) \right\|_{\infty} \leq 1 - \eta \quad (84)$$

holds with $\eta = \Delta/(2\|c_{S^*}^*\|_1)$, provided $\|c_{S^*}^*\|_1$ is bounded.

Proof. For each $k \notin S^*$, the k -th entry of the irrepresentable vector is $r_k := \Sigma_{k, S^*} \Sigma_{S^*, S^*}^{-1} \text{sign}(c_{S^*}^*)$. The signal correlation is $\langle \psi_k, u \rangle_{\mu} = \Sigma_{k, S^*} c_{S^*}^* + (\text{noise-free})$. By the KKT conditions of the population LASSO at the oracle solution, $|r_k| = |\Sigma_{k, S^*} \Sigma_{S^*, S^*}^{-1} \text{sign}(c_{S^*}^*)|$.

The SSC gap Δ ensures $|\langle \psi_k, u \rangle_{\mu}| \leq |\langle \psi_1, u \rangle_{\mu}| - \Delta$ for all $k \notin S^*$. Since the on-support correlation vector $\Sigma_{S^*} c_{S^*}^*$ has entries bounded by $\|c_{S^*}^*\|_1$, the normalized irrepresentable coefficient satisfies $|r_k| \leq 1 - \Delta/(2\|c_{S^*}^*\|_1)$. \square

A.7. Appendix G: Vandermonde Analysis

A.7 Vandermonde Conditioning and Orthogonal Polynomials

In this section, we address Assumption 2 (smooth block conditioning) for polynomial dictionaries. We demonstrate that while the naive monomial basis $\{x^k\}_{k=0}^K$ leads to exponentially ill-conditioned Gram matrices, the adoption of *orthogonal polynomials* renders Assumption 2 trivially satisfied with optimal constants.

A.7.1 The Monomial Basis: Hilbert Matrix Pathology

The monomial dictionary $\mathcal{M}_K = \{x^k\}_{k=0}^{K-1}$ in $L^2([0, 1], x^{\beta} dx)$ leads to exponentially ill-conditioned Gram matrices. In the classical $\beta = 0$ Hilbert-matrix case, $\kappa(G)$ grows exponentially with asymptotic base $(1 + \sqrt{2})^4$ and $\lambda_{\min}(G)$ decays exponentially; weighted variants remain exponentially ill-conditioned up to parameter-dependent constants. See [25, 34, 27] and Section B.

Implication: For the monomial basis, Assumption 2 fails catastrophically as $K \rightarrow \infty$. Any sparse recovery guarantee relying on $\lambda_{\min}^{\text{smooth}} > 0$ uniformly in K would require exponential sample complexity.

A.7.2 Orthogonal Polynomials: Perfect Conditioning

To resolve the ill-conditioning, we employ *Jacobi polynomials* $P_n^{(a,b)}(x)$, which are orthogonal with respect to the weight $(1-x)^a(1+x)^b$ on $[-1, 1]$.¹

Proposition 58 (Orthogonal Dictionary). *Let $\mathcal{P}_K = \{\phi_k\}_{k=0}^{K-1}$ where $\phi_k(x) = \frac{P_k^{(b,\beta)}(2x-1)}{\|P_k^{(b,\beta)}\|_{L^2(\mu)}}$ are the normalized shifted Jacobi polynomials. Then:*

1. *The Gram matrix is the identity: $\Sigma_{\text{smooth}} = I_K$.*
2. *Assumption 2 holds with $\lambda_{\min}^{\text{smooth}} = 1$ regardless of K or the specific subset $S_{\text{smooth}} \subset \{0, \dots, K-1\}$.*

Proof. By construction, $\langle \phi_i, \phi_j \rangle_\mu = \delta_{ij}$. Any submatrix of the identity matrix is itself an identity matrix, hence $\lambda_{\min}(\Sigma_{S_{\text{smooth}}, S_{\text{smooth}}}) = 1$ for any selection of $s-1$ smooth atoms. \square

A.7.3 Implications for Theorem 8

With orthogonal polynomials, the block decomposition in Theorem 8 simplifies:

- $\Sigma_{\text{smooth}} = I$ eliminates the condition number dependence on K .
- The cross-correlation vector ρ satisfies $\|\rho\|_2^2 \leq 1 - \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2$ via Bessel's inequality (Lemma 39), **independent of both s and K** .
- The minimum eigenvalue satisfies $\lambda_{\min}(\Sigma_{S^*}) \geq \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2/2$ uniformly for any $K \geq s$.

Practical Note: In numerical implementations (Section 3), we orthogonalize the smooth basis via QR decomposition or direct use of `scipy.special.eval_jacobi` to ensure numerical stability. This theoretical guarantee validates the experimental robustness observed across polynomial degrees up to $K = 24$.

A.8 Extension to Continuous Dictionaries via Covering Numbers

The results in Section A.5 assume the singular parameter lies on a finite grid. Here, we extend the recovery guarantee to the continuous manifold $\mathcal{M} = \{\psi_\alpha : \alpha \in \mathcal{A}\}$ using a metric entropy argument.

Lemma 59 (Lipschitz Continuity in L^2). *The mapping $\alpha \mapsto \psi_\alpha$ from the parameter space $\mathcal{A} \subset \mathbb{R}$ to the weighted Hilbert space L_w^2 is Lipschitz continuous. Specifically, for any $\alpha, \alpha' \in \mathcal{A}$:*

$$\|\psi_\alpha - \psi_{\alpha'}\|_w \leq L_{\max} |\alpha - \alpha'|, \quad (85)$$

where $L_{\max} = \sup_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \|\partial_\alpha \psi_\alpha\|_w < \infty$ is the constant evaluated in A.5.4.

Proof. By the Mean Value Theorem in Banach spaces, for any $\alpha, \alpha' \in \mathcal{A}$,

$$\|\psi_\alpha - \psi_{\alpha'}\|_w \leq \sup_{\xi \in [\alpha, \alpha']} \|\partial_\xi \psi_\xi\|_w \cdot |\alpha - \alpha'|.$$

The derivative $\partial_\alpha \psi_\alpha = c_\alpha \cdot x^\alpha \ln x + (\partial_\alpha c_\alpha) x^\alpha$ where $c_\alpha = \|x^\alpha\|_w^{-1}$. By the calculation in A.5.3, $\|\partial_\alpha \psi_\alpha\|_w^2 = \frac{1}{4} \mathcal{I}(\alpha)$, where $\mathcal{I}(\alpha)$ is the Fisher information. Since \mathcal{I} is continuous and positive on the compact set \mathcal{A} , we have $L_{\max} = \sup_{\alpha \in \mathcal{A}} \sqrt{\mathcal{I}(\alpha)}/4 < \infty$. \square

Theorem 60 (Resolution-Independent Recovery). *Consider a signal $u = c_1^* \psi_{\alpha^*} + u_{\text{smooth}}$ where $\alpha^* \in \mathcal{A}$ is arbitrary. Let $\eta > 0$ be the maximum tolerable modeling bias for exact support recovery. There exists a finite grid discretization $\mathcal{D}_{\text{grid}}$ of size K such that the LASSO estimator on this grid succeeds, provided:*

$$K \geq \frac{|c_1^*| L_{\max} |\mathcal{A}|}{\gamma \eta}. \quad (86)$$

¹**Notation convention:** Standard Jacobi polynomials $P_n^{(a,b)}$ use weight $(1-x)^a(1+x)^b$ on $[-1, 1]$. After the substitution $t = 2x - 1$ mapping $[0, 1] \rightarrow [-1, 1]$, the weight $x^\beta(1-x)^\alpha$ on $[0, 1]$ becomes $(1-t)^\beta((1+t)/2)^\alpha$. To obtain orthogonality with respect to $x^\beta(1-x)^\alpha$ on $[0, 1]$, we use $P_n^{(b,\beta)}(2x-1)$ (note: parameters in reverse order compared to the shifted weight). In `scipy.special.eval_jacobi(n, a, b, x)`, the first parameter is a , the second is b .

Proof. We construct a uniform δ -net $\mathcal{G} = \{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_K\}$ over \mathcal{A} with spacing $\delta = |\mathcal{A}|/K$. For any continuous $\alpha^* \in \mathcal{A}$, there exists a grid point $\alpha_k \in \mathcal{G}$ such that $|\alpha^* - \alpha_k| \leq \delta/2$. We approximate the continuous singular atom ψ_{α^*} by ψ_{α_k} . The approximation error acts as a structured noise term $z_{\text{bias}} = c_1^*(\psi_{\alpha^*} - \psi_{\alpha_k})$. By Lemma 59, the bias norm is bounded by:

$$\|z_{\text{bias}}\|_2 = |c_1^*| \|\psi_{\alpha^*} - \psi_{\alpha_k}\|_w \leq |c_1^*| L_{\max} \frac{\delta}{2}. \quad (87)$$

According to Proposition 3 (Robustness), the recovery error is bounded by $\|\hat{c} - c^*\|_2 \leq \frac{2}{\gamma} \|z_{\text{bias}}\|_2$. To ensure the error remains within the tolerance $\|\hat{c} - c^*\|_2 \leq \eta$, it suffices to enforce:

$$\frac{2}{\gamma} \left(|c_1^*| L_{\max} \frac{\delta}{2} \right) \leq \eta \quad \implies \quad \frac{|c_1^*| L_{\max} \delta}{\gamma} \leq \eta. \quad (88)$$

Substituting $\delta = |\mathcal{A}|/K$ and solving for K yields:

$$K \geq \frac{|c_1^*| L_{\max} |\mathcal{A}|}{\gamma \eta}.$$

This confirms that for any required precision η , a sufficiently fine finite grid exists to resolve the continuous parameter α^* . \square

Remark 61 (Extension to s -Sparse Signals via Covering Numbers). *For general s -sparse signals where smooth coefficients also vary continuously, the covering number argument extends by considering the product metric space of the parameter interval \mathcal{A} and the coefficient ball B_1^s .*

Specifically, let $\mathcal{N}(\mathcal{A}, \delta)$ denote the δ -covering number of \mathcal{A} in Euclidean distance. By standard metric entropy bounds [32],

$$\mathcal{N}(\mathcal{A} \times B_1^s, \delta) \leq \mathcal{N}(\mathcal{A}, \delta/2) \cdot \mathcal{N}(B_1^s, \delta/2) \leq \frac{|\mathcal{A}|}{\delta} \cdot \left(\frac{3}{\delta}\right)^s.$$

The grid size K thus scales as $O(\eta^{-1})$ in the singular parameter resolution, but exponentially in s (due to the coefficient discretization). In practice, for moderate sparsity $s \leq 10$, this overhead remains manageable.

A.9 Minimax Lower Bound and Optimality

We separate two lower-bound statements. The first is fully rigorous and uses a correlation gap parameter Δ . The second is a geometric reduction for κ_{pop} that requires an explicit packing assumption.

Theorem 62 (Rigorous detection lower bound in terms of Δ). *Consider a candidate class of size M and sub Gaussian noise with variance proxy σ^2 . If pairwise hypotheses are separated by correlation gap Δ , then any estimator with success probability at least $2/3$ must satisfy*

$$N \geq c_{\text{lb}} \frac{\sigma^2 \log M}{\Delta^2}, \quad (89)$$

for a universal constant $c_{\text{lb}} > 0$.

Proof. This is the standard Fano Le Cam testing bound for multi hypothesis detection with sub Gaussian observations. \square

Assumption 4 (Residual packing for κ_{pop} reduction). *There exists a subset of singular candidates $\{\alpha_m\}_{m=1}^M$ with $M \asymp D$ such that for residuals $r_m := \psi_{\alpha_m} - \text{proj}_{P_K} \psi_{\alpha_m}$:*

1. $\|r_m\|_{L^2(\mu)} \asymp \kappa_{\text{pop}}$ for all m .
2. $\|r_m - r_\ell\|_{L^2(\mu)} \gtrsim \kappa_{\text{pop}}$ for $m \neq \ell$.
3. Signal amplitude is scaled so that the induced testing gap is of order κ_{pop}^2 .

Proposition 63 (Geometric lower-rate reduction). *Under Assumption 4, any detector with success probability at least $2/3$ satisfies*

$$N \gtrsim \frac{\sigma^2 \log D}{\kappa_{\text{pop}}^4}. \quad (90)$$

Proof. Under Assumption 4, the testing radius is proportional to κ_{pop}^2 . Applying Theorem 62 with $\Delta \asymp \kappa_{\text{pop}}^2$ yields the claim. \square

Remark 64 (Interpretation of lower bounds). *The Δ based lower bound is fully rigorous and assumption free at the testing level. The κ_{pop}^{-4} rate is a geometric reduction that is rigorous conditional on Assumption 4. We therefore use it as structural evidence for scaling, not as a universal sharpness statement.*

Remark 65 (Upper-lower comparison). *The upper bound in Theorem 18 scales as $N \gtrsim s^{4\nu+2} \log D$ with $\nu = \alpha + \beta/2 + 1/2$. The lower side gives $N \gtrsim \sigma^2 \log D / \Delta^2$ unconditionally, and $N \gtrsim \sigma^2 \log D / \kappa_{\text{pop}}^4$ under Assumption 4. The remaining s factors are therefore concentration artifacts in the current proof route.*

B. Technical Notes on Fourth Moments, Conditioning, and Lower Bounds

Fourth Moment Operator Numerics

For shifted Jacobi atoms with $(\beta, b) = (0.55, 0)$ in the normalized $K = s$ ensemble, we compute

$$\mathbf{B}_{jk} = \int_0^1 \phi_j^2(x) \phi_k^2(x) w(x) dx$$

and fit $\|\mathbf{B}\|_{\text{op}} \approx C s^q$ on a log-log scale. The fit gives $q \approx 1.809$ on $s \in \{5, 10, 20, 50\}$. Representative values are:

s	$\ \mathbf{B}\ _{\text{op}}$
5	1.29×10^1
10	4.17×10^1
20	1.35×10^2
50	8.40×10^2

This is numerical evidence only; no theorem in this paper depends on this fitted exponent. Its main role is to motivate the small-ball route when K grows with s .

Monomial Basis Conditioning Pathology

For monomials $\{x^k\}_{k=0}^{K-1}$ under Jacobi-type weights, the Gram matrix is a generalized Hilbert matrix. Classical Hilbert-matrix asymptotics imply exponential condition-number growth, motivating the orthonormal Jacobi basis in Assumption 2. This is the quantitative reason we do not use raw monomials in the main guarantees.

Lower Bound Discussion Notes

The lower bound constructions are worst case and should be interpreted as scaling guidance, not as sharp instance level thresholds. Two caveats are central:

- Packing constructions control the hardest geometric configurations, not favorable instances where $\kappa(\alpha^*) \gg \kappa_{\text{pop}}$.
- Constants depend on the testing family and are not tuned to finite- D practical regimes.

These caveats do not change the role of κ_{pop} as the geometric driver, but they matter for quantitative prediction.

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